

Pathos

Open Science Impact Pathways

Deliverable D1.3 (update)

Key Impact Pathways for the open science framework

Deliverable Number and Name	D1.3 (update) Key Impact Pathways for the open science framework
Due Date	M34
Delivery Date	M36
Work Package	Work Package 1
Type	Report
Author (v2)	Lennart Stoy (TGB), Elisa Seminaroti (TGB), Izabella Martins Grapengiesser (TGB), Nicki Lisa Cole (KNOW), Lena Tsipouri (OPIX), Tereza Simova (OpenAIRE)
Reviewers (v2)	Nicki Lisa Cole (KNOW)
Approved by	
Dissemination Level	Public
Version	2.0
Number of Pages	78

The information in this document reflects only the author's views and the European Commission is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein. The information in this document is provided "as is" without guarantee or warranty of any kind, express or implied, including but not limited to the fitness of the information for a particular purpose. The user thereof uses the information at his/ her sole risk and liability.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe framework programme under grant agreement No. 101058728. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the European Research Executive Agency can be held responsible for them.

Revision History

VERSION	DATE	REASON	REVISED BY
0.1	30 January	Initial structure and first contents	Lennart Stoy (TGB), Istvan Karasz (TGB)
0.2	12 March 2024	First partial draft for internal review	Lennart Stoy (TGB), Elisa Seminaroti (TGB), Izabella Martins Grapengiesser (TGB)
	28 March 2024	1 st Internal Review	Viola Peter (TGB), Nicki Lisa Cole (KNOW), Vincent Traag (CWTS)
0.3	9 April 2024	Full draft	Lennart Stoy (TGB), Elisa Seminaroti (TGB), Izabella Martins Grapengiesser (TGB)
1.0		Version 1	
1.1	1 October 2024	Update of structure	Lennart Stoy (TGB)
1.2	14 July 2025	Update of section 2 and 3	Lennart Stoy (TGB),
1.3	16 July 2025	Open Access pathway (update)	Elisa Seminaroti (TGB), Lennart Stoy (TGB), Izabella Martins Grapengiesser (TGB),
		Research data sharing pathway	Izabella Martins Grapengiesser (TGB), Elisa Seminaroti (TGB), Lennart Stoy (TGB), Lena Tsipouri (OPIX), Tereza Simova (OpenAIRE)
		Citizen Science pathway (update)	Lennart Stoy (TGB), Nicki Lisa Cole (KNOW)
		Reproducibility pathway	Elisa Seminaroti (TGB), Lennart Stoy (TGB)
		Software pathway	Elisa Seminaroti (TGB), Lennart Stoy (TGB), Izabella Martins Grapengiesser (TGB)
		Environment pathway	Lennart Stoy (TGB)
1.4	17 July 2025	Update of Section 1, 5	Lennart Stoy (TGB)
	30 July 2025	Review	Nicki Lisa Cole (KNOW)
1.5	28 August 2025	Full updated draft and section 6	Elisa Seminaroti (TGB), Lennart Stoy (TGB)
2.0	29 August	Version 2	Elisa Seminaroti (TGB), Lennart Stoy (TGB)

Table 1: Document Revision History

Table of Contents

Disclaimer	6
Abbreviations	7
Executive Summary	8
1. Introduction	9
2. Approach	10
3. Data collection and analysis	13
3.1. Sources	13
3.2. Coding of information	14
3.3. Data summary	18
3.4. Initial mapping	19
3.5. Recasting and explication of assumptions	19
4. Key Impact Pathways	20
4.1. Open Access	22
4.1.1. Pathway mapping	22
4.1.1. Key impact pathways	26
4.1.1. Discussion	31
4.1.2. Indicators and metrics	31
4.1.3. Case study	32
4.2. Open and FAIR research data	34
4.2.1. Pathway mapping	35
4.2.2. Key impact pathway	36
4.2.1. Discussion	38
4.2.2. Indicators and metrics	39

4.2.3. Case study.....	40
4.3. Citizen Science	41
4.3.1. Pathway mapping	43
4.3.2. Key impact pathway.....	44
4.3.1. Discussion	46
4.3.2. Indicators and metrics.....	47
4.4. Open code and software	48
4.4.1. Pathway mapping	49
4.4.2. Key impact pathway.....	50
4.4.3. Discussion	52
4.4.4. Indicators and metrics.....	53
4.5. Environment.....	54
4.5.1. Pathway mapping	55
4.5.2. Key impact pathway.....	56
4.5.3. Discussion	57
4.5.4. Indicators	58
4.6. Reproducibility.....	59
4.6.1. Pathway mapping	59
4.6.2. Key impact pathway.....	61
4.6.3. Discussion	63
4.6.4. Indicators and metrics.....	64
5. Limitations of the approach and evidence	65
6. Conclusions	68
References.....	69

List of Tables

Table 1: Document Revision History	2
Table 2 Definitions of individual steps.....	11
Table 3 Data extraction fiche	15
Table 4 Codes for activities: Open Science areas	16
Table 5 Codes for outcomes and impacts.....	17
Table 6 Impact code occurrence.....	18

List of Figures

Figure 3-1 Depiction of individual steps	15
Figure 4-1 Initial Mapping for Gold Open Access	23
Figure 4-2 Initial Mapping for Hybrid Open Access.....	24
Figure 4-3 Initial mapping for Green open access.....	25
Figure 4-4 Key Impact Pathway for Gold and Hybrid Open Access.....	27
Figure 4-5 Key Impact Pathway for Green Open Access.....	29
Figure 4-6 Initial Mapping for Open/FAIR data	35
Figure 4-7 Key Impact Pathway for Open and FAIR Data	37
Figure 4-8 Initial mapping for citizen science.....	44
Figure 4-9 Key Impact Pathway for Citizen Science.....	45
Figure 4-10 Initial Mapping for open code/software	50
Figure 4-11 Final Pathway for open code/software	51
Figure 4-12 Initial mapping for environment.....	56
Figure 4-13 Key Impact Pathway for environment.....	57
Figure 4-14 Initial mapping for reproducibility.....	60
Figure 4-15 Final pathway for Reproducibility	61

Disclaimer

This document contains description of the PathOS project findings, work and products. Certain parts of it might be under partner Intellectual Property Right (IPR) rules so, prior to using its content please contact the consortium head for approval.

In case you believe that this document harms in any way IPR held by you as a person or as a representative of an entity, please do notify us immediately.

The authors of this document have taken any available measure in order to ensure that its content is accurate, consistent and lawful. However, neither the project consortium as a whole nor the individual partners that implicitly or explicitly participated in the creation and publication of this document hold any sort of responsibility that might occur as a result of using its content.

This publication has been produced with the assistance of the European Union. The content of this publication is the sole responsibility of the PathOS consortium and can in no way be taken as a reflection of the views of the European Union.

PathOS is a project funded by the European Union (Grant Agreement No 101058728).

Abbreviations

APC	Article Processing Charge
COVID-19	Coronavirus Disease
CS	Citizen Science
D	Deliverable
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
ID	Identifier
IPR	Intellectual Property Right
KIP	Key Impact Pathway
OA	Open Access
OS	Open Science
OSTP	White House Office of Science and Technology Policy
PathOS	Open Science Impact Pathways (Horizon Europe Project)
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization

Executive Summary

Open Science is an umbrella term for a variety of different practices in public and private research,. With the growing interest in Open Science, for example through the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science in 2021, there is also a need for better understanding the diverse impacts of Open Science practices.

Based on literature and case studies collected by PathOS, the report presents Key Impact Pathways of Open Science. The approach used for the report was tested in a preceding proof-of-concept study and adapts common evaluation methods and concepts, particularly identifying impact pathways (from activities to the creation of outputs, outcomes, and impacts).

The resulting information is used to generate high-level impact pathways, displayed as intervention logics, of Open Science practices. Six such pathways indicating the impacts of different Open Science activities are identified in the report:

- A *Citizen Science pathway* illustrates how citizen science interventions correlate with certain impacts such as ‘trust’ stemming from the outcome of engagement of citizens in citizen science projects.
- Two *Open Access pathway* were generated through a “downstream” analysis and highlight the diverse effects of two different types of Open Access publishing.
- One pathway explores the impacts of *research data sharing* through Open and FAIR Data, showing different economic effects and benefits.
- An exploratory pathway, due to limited available evidence, discusses the potential impacts of *open code and open software* sharing.
- In addition potential pathways for impacts of Open Science on the *environment*. The findings illustrate the important mediating factor of policy and governance, which can be affected by a broad range of societal aspects.
- Likewise, another pathway presents the ways Open Science can affect *reproducibility*.

The report shows that Both tracing the effects of different Open Science interventions up to the impact stage (“downstream analysis”) and identifying the activities that may create certain academic, societal, and economic impacts (“upstream analysis”) are feasible. While the approach is overall confirmed, the results also point to the need for further research in terms of topical coverage and types of evidence, as well as limitations to the causal claims for Open science impacts.

1. Introduction

Open Science is an umbrella term for a variety of different practices in public and private research, including Open Access to research publications, Open/FAIR data, Citizen Science, Open peer review, Open Code/Software, among other practices. With the growing salience of these practices at the international level, for example through the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science in 2021 (UNESCO, 2021) and its integration into funding programmes and requirements worldwide (OSTP, 2022; European Commission, 2021a), there is also increasing attention to the impact(s) these practices are intended to create. This attention goes hand in hand with growing interest in refining and extending the monitoring of Open Science practices.¹

The *PathOS – Open Science Impact Pathways* project (<http://pathos-project.eu>) fills an important gap related to monitoring and impact assessment by investigating the state of the art of Open Science impacts. It provides conceptual frameworks (Dekker et al., 2023), indicators (Apartis et al., 2025)², case studies (Cole et al., 2023), and a scoping review of evidence (Klebel et al., 2024; Klebel et al. 2025, Cole et al., 2024, Tsipouri et al. 2025). These tools are intended to assist stakeholders, such as researchers, institutions, funders, and policymakers, to better understand the impacts of Open Science and to conceptualise and design policy and research strategies based on evidence. It also aims to aid the monitoring initiatives mentioned above to create and refine impact-oriented monitoring frameworks.

A specific challenge identified by PathOS is the availability of evidence about the tangible effects of Open Science practices. A large-scale scoping review of existing academic and other literature (Klebel et al., 2023; Cole et al., 2024,) conducted by the project showed, depending on the area of Open Science, evidence for impact is lacking. Additional conceptual work by the project has also explored the challenges in attributing causal effects to practices of Open Science (Klebel and Traag, 2024). A key ambition of PathOS is therefore to better understand what type of impacts in the academic, economic, and societal realm can be proven to be caused by Open Science practices.

This report summarises six *Key Impact Pathways* of Open Science practices identified by PathOS. Impact pathways are frameworks used to design and evaluate policy programmes, projects, and other types of interventions originally developed by Rabl & Peuportier (1995). In the EU,

¹ See <https://open-science-monitoring.org/>

² See the online version at <https://handbook.pathos-project.eu>

the concept has been further developed to identify, for example, environmental impacts of research and innovation policy (Miedzinski et al., 2013).

With this report, we aim to provide a structured investigation of the existing evidence through the lens of impact pathways from activity to output to outcome to impact. The primary objective of this deliverable is therefore to identify Key Impact Pathways (KIPs) of Open Science. It does so by applying the step-by-step method described in PathOS D1.1 (Dekker et al., 2023), following the piloting of the approach in the previous version of the report with a limited body of evidence on three impact pathways (Karasz et al., 2024).

The report is structured as follows. Chapter 1 is this introduction. Chapter 2 briefly describes the conceptual background, in particular the Key Impact Pathway approach. Chapter 3 presents the data collection and analytic approach employed for this report. Chapter 4 presents six identified Key Impact Pathways. Chapter 5 briefly discusses limitations of the chosen approach. Chapter 6 summarises the report.

2. Approach

This report follows the approach described in a previous deliverable of the PathOS project (Dekker et al., 2023). The approach borrows concepts usually used in the context of policy and programme evaluation, particularly the concept of an intervention logic (of a programme, policy, etc.). Such intervention logic models (or impact chain model) aim to (re)construct the internal intervention logic of the staff designing the intervention, while structuring the intervention in logical sequence from activities to the creation of outputs, outcomes, and impacts.

Intervention logics are usually a practitioner's tools to design policies, programmes, projects, and other interventions, and to study and evaluate them against their impact and other criteria such as effectiveness, efficiency, coherence and relevance. Their main purpose is to explicate the assumptions about causal effect chains to reach a specific objective through an intervention. Commonly used, for example in the context of the EU Better Regulation Guidelines (European Commission, 2021b), their development is closely tied to the use of qualitative and quantitative indicators for each step of the intervention logic. Therefore, they should support the identification of suitable types of evidence for causal effects at each step.

The PathOS project has adopted commonly used definitions. Open science impacts are defined by PathOS as "long-lasting, elementary and wide-spread change that affect different segments of society, economy, and academia, and therefore the environment in general" (Dekker et al., 2023). For Key Impact Pathways (KIPs) PathOS applies the definition of "the most important or

relevant pathways” (ibid.) to achieve a certain impact. The definitions for activity, output, outcome, and impact are shown in Table 3 below.

Table 2 Definitions of individual steps

Step	Definition
Activity	Actions that lead to the (desired) outputs.
Output	Directly related measurable effects of activities that can be controlled by the initiators of the intervention.
Outcome	The likely or achieved short-term and medium-term effects of the outputs (mostly measurable social, economic and academic changes). There is only limited (or no) control by the intervention initiator.
Impact	Long-lasting, elementary and wide-spread change that affects different segments of society, economy, and academia, and therefore the environment in general. Impacts can be caused by multiple stakeholder interventions, and multiple stakeholders can be affected. Impacts can be direct or indirect, intended or unintended, relate to behavioural and/or systemic changes.

The approach applied by PathOS took a stepwise approach to derive intervention logic diagrams from the collected evidence. This was done in two main steps, derived from (Wilkinson et al., 2021). First, a ‘system map’ was created, providing a comprehensive picture of all activities, outputs, outcomes and impacts collected through the data collection. Second, the map was recast into a Theory of Change, by developing a “logical sequence’ from input to outcome” (ibid, p87). Here, activities, inputs, and key assumptions and uncertainties were also explicated. This method, which follows an iterative process based on data collection, recasting, and explicating underlying assumptions, permits “upstream” and “downstream” analysis of the data (Wilkinson et al., 2021).

In the approach followed for this report, we adapted Wilkinson’s approach in three steps. First, data was collected from the available evidence (See Chapter 3) and analysed to identify how activities, outputs, and outcomes were linked, forming impact chains. This step included the coding of activities, outputs, outcomes, and societal, academic, or economic impacts . A key difference to Wilkinson et al. (2021) was that the approach for this report does not employ participatory system mapping but was based on secondary data analysis. Participatory systems mapping is an approach which develops directed cyclic graphs as “causal models of a system, represented by a network of factors and their causal relations” (Barbrook-Johnson & Penn, 2022). Given the large amount of data collected through PathOS, this data was chosen for consistency to develop the systems mapping, instead of a participatory method.

In the second step, based on this cumulation of evidence, the impact chains emanating from specific interventions (i.e., Open Science practices) are isolated and displayed visually. These were then recast into initial impact chains with a logical sequence. With this, we aimed to identify the range of impacts chains resulting from these more detailed interventions. In this step, an iterative and participatory element was introduced through involvement of the wider project consortium discussing the identified sequences and through validation with stakeholders. The usage of the codes assigned in step one, which were aligned with further project work, also allowed linking the results to the PathOS indicator handbook and case studies.

In the third step we enriched the identified causal chains with more detailed contextual information from the original data sources, such as articles and PathOS case studies underlying assumptions,. This was an important step to explain the context of each identified pathway, including the conditions that were necessary to give rise to specific effects. In this way, we rendered the identified pathways a more useful tool for readers and stakeholders. The results of this exercise are the description of context and limiting factors for each key impact pathway presented in Chapter 4.

It must be acknowledged that the described approach diverged from the usual application of intervention logics for an ex-post evaluation of past actions. For instance, an ex-post evaluation should be conducted against the initial programme objectives and chosen indicators at every stage, including the inputs provided, such as funding, personnel, legislative reforms, etc. With the evidence collected for PathOS being based on a post hoc selection and coding of findings for impacts, often without link to specific inputs, the direct usability for such ex-post assessments is limited.

In addition, a key difference lies in the usage of the term *Key Impact Pathway* by PathOS. The results presented later in Section 4 are much closer to linear intervention logics or theories of change. They are simplified representations of effects, with specific focus on the chain of effects stemming from individual interventions. It is possible to understand such impact chains as an *adaptation of structural causal models* (see Klebel and Traag, 2024). Such models provide a visual representation of causal links, verified by evidence, but “not whether that effect is linear, exponential or an ‘interaction’ with some other effects” (Klebel and Traag, 2024, p. 2). Such models provide structural assumptions about effect chains of Open Science practices but should not be used as predictive tools. It was therefore crucial to explain the causal assumptions and limitations of the final pathways through the third step.

Considering the chosen approach and the evidence it incorporates, the pathways developed in PathOS should be mainly treated as tools that help stakeholders *access and navigate the*

uncovered evidence for effects and impacts of Open Science practices. They are not an attempt to prove that any Open Science practice will always create the exact same effects identified by the research done in PathOS, as this is dependent on contextual conditions, inputs and other factors. Interpreted from the other end, that is the type of impact, they should be understood as devices that help identify possible interventions. Their use is therefore intended for forward-looking programmes or project design.

3. Data collection and analysis

3.1. Sources

To be able to implement the approach described in section 2, suitable data had to be selected. We utilised the collective effort of the project partners, their different deliverables and ongoing works. In particular, the literature scoping exercise and case studies were used as data sources.

Literature as information source

As part of a scoping review of literature (cite D1.2), the PathOS project identified 706 relevant academic articles and other types of literature which contained information on impacts of Open Science. These documents were categorized based on impact area into academia (485 documents), society (196 documents), and the economy (27 documents). The list of documents was made available online in the form of a Zotero library.³

The prior collected information, in particular collected information about study details, study aims, key findings, as well as the abstract and full text enabled the team to select relevant publications for the scope of this deliverable. This selection took place when the document indicated elements of an individual intervention logic, which was also supported by quantitative or qualitative evidence. Specifically, the documents were screened for a description of concrete *activities*, the description of *outputs* of these activities, as well as the description of *outcomes* and *impacts*. The additional screening step, although time consuming, was necessary since the scoping review did not entail a systematic screening according to the definitions applied for the impact pathways. Nor did all publications relate to sufficiently detailed 'steps' in the Key Impact Pathway framework, such as activities or interventions. When no such information could be extracted, documents were excluded following discussion among the study team. The

³ Thomas Klebel, Nicki Lisa Cole, Lena Tsipouri, Eva Kormann, Istvan Karasz, Sofia Liarti, Lennart Stoy, Vincent Traag, Silvia Vignetti, Alkis Pitelis, Ioanna Grypari, Simon Apartis, & Tony Ross-Hellauer. (2023). Data from "PathOS - D1.2 Scoping Review of Open Science Impact" (v1.1) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7969951>

definitions for each step used by PathOS correspond to those in Table 2 above. Following this screening of the 706 publications, 196 publications were found to contain sufficient evidence for 'steps' of impact pathways and included in the sample used for this report.

Case studies as data source

PathOS also includes six case studies of different Open Science initiatives, which are reported in PathOS D3.1 (Cole et al., 2023, D3.3 Open Science Impact Indicators for Case studies Final report (forthcoming)). The case studies were developed in parallel to the literature review. Therefore, they were not used as further evidence during the preparation of this updated deliverable. Case studies and their intervention logics were consulted during the review of the draft pathways as part of Step 2 of the approach explained above. Nonetheless, the experience in incorporating and coding the draft impact pathway for the UniProt case study as part of the initial version of this report (Karasz et al., 2024) confirms the possibility to incorporate them systematically.

3.2. Coding of information

Since the objective of this deliverable is to delineate Key Impact Pathways based on evidence collected from diverse sources, we scrutinized the selected sources (196 documents) with the aim of uncovering individual impact pathways from source documents.

For the collection and analysis of data, the project developed a data extraction form (Table 3) to process information in a standardised way, to support the next step. Data in this context means qualitative information about the source document and the identified steps in the impact chains. The data extraction fiche helped us to assign the collected information to the impact chain components of activity, output, outcome, and impact, as well as to impact areas.

Learning from the previous version of this report, minor revisions were introduced to the data extraction fiche. These revisions included the addition of optional information on relevant stakeholders, related indicators, type of evidence and confidence in the evidence. The latter two, type and confidence of evidence, refer to the assessment done for the initial data charting during the scoping review phase, where available. The former two, stakeholders and indicators, were added to retain information relevant to identify the concerned stakeholders and possible indicators from the PathOS Open Science Indicator Handbook (Apartis et al., 2025).

In addition, the data extraction fiche also permits the tracking of each coded step, its source information, the text extract, etc. This also provides transparency, facilitating reproduction of the work undertaken by the study team.

Table 3 Data extraction fiche

Variable	Description
Source	Name of case study OR ID of paper OR relevant D1.2 chapter
Type of source	Case study OR literature
When	Date of extraction into fiche
Who	Name or initials of researcher doing the coding
Quote/text	Copy of relevant text (e.g., "key findings" from data charting), where feasible
Description of logic	Short description of intervention logic (optional)
Step (Cause)	Select one: Activity, Output, Outcome, short-term Impact, Long-term impact
Type (Cause)	Select one: from coding table or add additional one
Step (Effect)	Select one: Input, Output, Outcome, long-term impact
Type (Effect)	Select one: from coding table or add additional one
Direction of change	Select: Increase OR Decrease
Stakeholders	<i>Affected stakeholders (optional)</i>
Related indicators	<i>Indicator (optional)</i>
Type of evidence	<i>Type of evidence from scoping review (optional)</i>
Confidence	<i>Confidence assessment from scoping review (optional)</i>
Comment	Any comment (optional)

Source: Technopolis Group

The next analytic step included the extraction of impact chains identified in the selected sources. They were coded in the individual steps from input to output, from output to outcome, from outcome to short-term impact and from short-term impact to long-term impact (see Figure 3-1). Each first component of a step was labelled as “cause” and each second component of a step was labelled as ‘effect’ in the data set.

Figure 3-1 Depiction of individual steps

The extracted information was arranged in a spreadsheet in which each row represents a single “step” between two components which contains each element of the data extraction fiche

displayed in Table 3. With regards to the *Activity*, the predefined Open Science areas were used (Table 4).

Table 4 Codes for activities: Open Science areas

Activity type	Code
Open Science	Open Access
	Open/FAIR Data
	Citizen Science
	Open Code / Software
	Open Methods (including infrastructures such as EOSC)
	Open Evaluation and Assessment
	Open infrastructure (EOSC)

Source: Technopolis Group

Concerning *Outputs*, the list was expanded and revised compared to the first version of the report to better represent the diversity of different outputs across Open Science practices. For example, the generic code ‘*Availability of Open Publications*’ was replaced by more granular code representing Gold and Green open access, hybrid, books, and preprint publications. The full list of outputs included the following codes:

- Availability of Open Platforms
- Availability of Open/FAIR data
- Availability of OA publications (gold)
- Availability of OA publication (green/preprint)⁴
- Availability of OA publication (books)
- Availability of OA publication (diamond)
- Availability of OA publication (hybrid)
- Preregistrations
- Availability of Open code/software
- Open Peer Reviews

To link these outputs with outcomes and impact, a set of codes describing outcomes and impacts displayed in **Error! Not a valid bookmark self-reference.** was used. These were slightly updated following the initial version of this report. Two codes were removed to streamline the list and avoid overlaps, namely “costs” and “participation”.

⁴ Green and preprints were combined due to the reliance on repository infrastructure instead of publisher-side Open Access, affecting especially the economic impacts of these two types.

Table 5 Codes for outcomes and impacts

Area	Code
Academic impact	Citations
	Collaboration
	Efficiency
	Equity
	Integrity
	Interdisciplinarity
	Novelty
	Productivity
	Quality
	Re-use
	Reproducibility
	Trust
	Readership
Societal impact	Climate/Environment
	COVID-19
	Diversity
	Education and awareness
	Empowerment
	Engagement
	Equity
	Equity
	Gender
	Health
	Policy and governance
	Privacy/ethics
	SDGs (generic)
Economic impact	Collaboration
	Cost savings
	Efficiency
	Re-use and absorption of academic knowledge by economic actors
	Innovation
	Labour market impacts
	Patenting
	Productivity
	Science-industry collaboration
	Socially relevant products and processes
Uptake of research results by industry	

Source: Technopolis Group

Several types of impact may be present across the areas of academic, societal, and economic impact. For example, equity and trust are listed as both academic and societal impact. Collaboration appears both as an academic and economic impact. Nonetheless, these codes

have different definitions depending on whether they occurred under societal or academic impact.

3.3. Data summary

Following the screening of sources and coding of information, the dataset comprises information stemming from a total of 196 individual sources. Additionally, each article extracted from the scoping review literature is treated as an individual source (Table 6).

In total, the screening and coding exercise across the 196 sources resulted in the identification of 670 individual steps. These were found from Activity to Output (n=232), Output to Outcome (n=268), Outcome to Short-term Impact (n=115), and Short-Term Impact to Long-Term Impact (n=26).

In addition, several horizontal and other connections were found and coded. This part contained connections between Outcome and Outcome (n=7), Outcome and Long-Term Impact (n=10), Short-Term Impact and Short-Term Impact (n=4), and Long-Term Impact and Long-Term impact (n=1). Horizontal connections represent correlations between different effects (e.g., outcomes, impacts) which co-occur.

The coding found a total of 156 individual short-term and long-term impacts. These were distributed over 28 different codes spanning all three areas (Table 6).

Table 6 Impact code occurrence

Impact	Long term impact	Short term impact	Total
Behavioural change	1	3	4
Citations		11	11
Climate/Environment	10	5	15
Collaboration		2	2
Cost savings	1	8	9
Economic growth	5		5
Efficiency	2	3	5
Empowerment		1	1
Engagement		1	1
Equity		6	6
Health	3	9	12
Innovation	1	4	5
Knowledge spillover		2	2
Labour market impacts	1	3	4
Novelty		1	1

Patenting		1	1
Policy and governance	1	5	6
Productivity		5	5
Quality		4	4
Re-use		3	3
Re-use and absorption of academic knowledge by societal actors		9	9
Readership		2	2
Relevant products and Services		5	5
Reproducibility		8	8
SDG solutions (generic)	7	13	20
Tax revenue	5		5
Trust		3	3
Uptake of research results by industry		2	2
Total	37	119	156

Source: Technopolis Group

The underlying data is available as a separate annex to this report.⁵

3.4. Initial mapping

The extracted data can be displayed visually as a graph. The graphs display the density of connections and allows arranging the flow from activities to impacts, which suites the idea of isolating and identifying overarching effect chains. The visual display can also reveal initial clusters.

3.5. Recasting and explication of assumptions

Following the approach outlined in Section 2, the last step includes the recasting and refocussing of the overall mapping towards a Theory of Change. For the purposes of PathOS, as explained above, we treat these refocused visualisations, starting from a specific Open Science activity, as our main chains of impact (“Key Impact Pathways”).

⁵ The data set is available on Zenodo at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16993959>.

The process starts with a selection of the relevant intervention.⁶ To do so practically, a sequential process was employed to identify a chain spanning from a given activity to all relevant effects emanating from this activity and its individual effects.

- 1) Identify all connections starting at a given activity and the frequency with which they lead to a certain output.
- 2) Identify all connections starting at each of these outputs and the frequency with which they lead to a certain outcome.
- 3) Identify all connections starting at each of these outcomes and the frequency with which they lead to a certain short-term impact.
- 4) Identify all connections starting at each of these short-term impacts and the frequency with which they lead to a certain short-term long-term impact.

Based on this approach, the selected connections were inserted into the same tool as used for the overall mapping introduced in the previous section. This results in an initial visual mapping of all effects that may be attributed to the given Open Science intervention. Recasting may include different means:

- Rearranging elements according to the impact chain from activity to impact
- Removal of steps and components with low frequency
- Limitation of horizontal connections
- Clustering of related codes

For instance, an impact found once in the source data as an effect of an intervention may be less relevant to “the most important or relevant pathways” according to the definitions used by the PathOS project. These judgments required knowledge of the underlying evidence, since the frequency of occurrence in the data is not necessarily an indicator of effect size, and were therefore discussed and validated in the by different means. In the first instance, this included the team of authors. In addition, workshops among project partners, were conducted to confirm or refine the “recasting” conducted by the author team.

4. Key Impact Pathways

Building on the initial version of this deliverable, which presented three different pilot pathways testing the approach, this version presents six revised and new Key Impact Pathways. The

⁶ Other selection choices can be used, for example a group of activities, a group of impacts, but the data can also be filtered by the type of source material such as case studies, individual papers, since they were included as variables in the data fiche.

pathways were selected based on different considerations. First, four pathways highlight impact pathways of key Open Science practices, including Open Access publishing, Citizen Science, and research data sharing. Growing practices, namely open research software and open evaluation, were selected to identify emerging trends and gaps.

These pathways use a “downstream analysis” approach that started with the selection of specific interventions, aiming to uncover the different effects of specific Open Science practices:

- Chapter 4.1 is a profound revision of the original impact pathway starting from Open Access activities. The updated version distinguishes between impacts of different types of Open Access publishing.
- Chapter 4.2 showcases the key impacts of research data sharing in the form of Open and FAIR data
- Chapter 4.3 is an update of the original impact pathway starting from Citizen Science activities.
- Chapter 4.4 summarises the evidence related to the emerging effects of Open code/software.

Two further pathways use an “upstream analysis” approach. For these, the analysis started with the selection of an impact code, then identified the relevant Open Science practices, outputs and outcomes that lead up to the impact:

- Chapter 4.5 updates the original pathway leading to different environmental impacts.
- Chapter 4.6 takes the example of activities contributing to reproducibility.

Each pathway is related to other outputs of PathOS. Example indicators for Open Science practices and their effects are highlighted from the indicator handbook (Apartis et al., 2025). In addition, short summaries of relevant PathOS case studies are presented where relevant.

The interventions displayed in the next sections are *generalisations* of the evidence found for the impacts of Open Science practices. For example, when an activity mentions “Open Data”, this must be understood as the spectrum of activities which can result in an increase of open research data. Examples have been added to the visuals of the Key Impact Pathways. While the use of such –catch-all terms unfortunately reduces the specificity of each pathway, a detailed analysis of all possible interventions under these catch-all terms would be beyond the scope of

the project which focuses on the high-level impacts of a range of Open Science areas (e.g., Open Access, Citizen Science), not individual projects.⁷

4.1. Open Access

Open Access refers to making research outputs freely available, allowing everyone to access, download, read and use material produced by others. Its primary goal is to allow everyone to access and re-use academic work, fostering knowledge sharing and research advancement.

There are pathways to Open Access, for example based on the degree of accessibility via Creative Commons licenses, the location where the content is made available, or the question of costs. These models are commonly identified by "colours", such as Gold Open Access for publications made available by the publisher or Green Open Access, where publications are shared via repositories. Beyond these two well-established models, several other variations exist which are not explained by colours. Hybrid OA is a model where journals publish articles both free of charge and subscription based. Diamond OA, instead, eliminates publication fees for both authors and readers. Platinum OA also does not charge fees to authors, but covers costs through alternative means such as donations, grants, or subsidies. Bronze OA refers to publications that are freely accessible on the publisher's website, but without open license for reuse. In the wake of the transition to Open Access, the question which publishing model best achieves an equitable and financially sustainable scholarly publishing system has increasingly garnered attention by policy makers (Council of the European Union, 2023).

4.1.1. Pathway mapping

For this report, the downstream effects of **Open Access** practices were identified based on a "**downstream analysis**". That is, the pathway was constructed starting with the selection of 'Open Access' as the origin point. Resulting from activities related to Open Access are specific outputs, outcomes and impacts.

The mapping process is based on sources included in the initial data screening, performed for the drafting of PathOS Deliverable D1.3 Key Impact Pathways for the Open Science Framework (Karasz et al., 2024), as well as additional sources analysed in a second phase of the work.

⁷ However, learnings from the exercise and feedback from the stakeholder workshop carried out in March 2024 also pointed out that more specificity would be useful, for example covering specific interventions, inputs etc.

The focus of this report is on the outcomes and impacts resulting from Open Access publishing, identifying high-level impact pathways of the following Open Access routes:

- **Gold Open Access** – Publications are made freely accessible directly through the publisher.
- **Green Open Access** – Publications, often preprints or Author Accepted Manuscripts, are made freely available on repositories. However, access to these documents may be delayed due to a publisher-imposed embargo.
- In addition, we also investigate effects of **Hybrid Open Access** models, which combines subscription-based journals with open access to individual articles. It allows authors to pay an APC to make specific articles freely accessible, while the rest of the journal content remains subscription based.

Following the process outlined in Section 2, initial mappings for Gold, Hybrid and Green Open Access publications are shown respectively in Figure 4-1, Figure 4-2, and Figure 4-3.

Figure 4-1 Initial Mapping for Gold Open Access

Figure 4-2 Initial Mapping for Hybrid Open Access

Figure 4-3 Initial mapping for Green open access

The initial mapping revealed certain common trends and signs of effects across the different types of Open Access publications. Notably, there are links between the availability of Open Access publications and **citations** (Boselli and Galindo-Rueda, 2019). Besides citations, positive effects on **readership** reflect the increased media attention and visibility of research. Altmetrics, for instance, assess shares and mentions of research outputs on various platforms, including social media, news websites, blogs and more. Our literature review indicates that Open Access publications have an overall positive impact on citation in posts, as well as visibility on social media (Cho, 2021).

The re-use of knowledge by a diverse range of actors emerged as another key common outcome of OA publications upon further examination of the downstream effects. The analysis also indicated positive outcomes related to **quality** and **productivity** of research and more, such as **collaboration**.

Costs appear in all three mappings and require further attention. Monetary flows in Open Access publishing can appear at different stages. For example, they can be understood as inputs, as investments in Open Access infrastructure, or payment for article processing charges.

Costs also occur as savings when publications are accessible without paywalls. Thus, costs appear in all pathways but with differing expressions.

4.1.1. Key impact pathways

The next step taken by the research team was to simplify and refine the mapping to improve its clarity and make it easier to understand. This process involved consolidating related concepts to reduce redundancy and ensure a more coherent representation of the pathways. Closely related categories under the umbrella of the Sustainable Development Goals such as health, climate/environment, and 'SDG solutions' were grouped into a single SDGs category, reflecting their common objective of addressing sustainable development. Similarly, "Engagement" was combined with "Collaboration," as both involve cooperation between different stakeholders. We also unified "Re-use" with "Re-use by societal actors" to capture the broader implications of knowledge and resource reuse in a single category. "Patenting" was grouped with "innovation," and "tax revenue" with "economic growth," summarising the overall impact on economic development. These adjustments were made to streamline the mapping, making it more concise while still capturing the essential relationships between the concepts.

After the simplification of the initial findings, the pathway was discussed and validated together with the PathOS consortium and structured in the form of two Key Impact Pathways as shown below. Two separate Key Impact Pathways were developed due to the observed similarities between the mapping of effects of both Gold and Hybrid Open Access. As a result, and considering that there are only limited sources available concerning hybrid Open Access for publications, we decided to develop a common final pathway for these two models. The effects for Green Open Access were treated separately.

Both Key Impact Pathways are based on a common structure, which served as a basis for drafting the various pathways. The presence of inputs, outputs, outcomes and impacts was adapted according to the specific model of Open Access, by greying out those not applicable. During the development of the two Key Impact Pathways, due to limited evidence, we opted to exclude "Relevant products and services" from the pathways, as it was difficult to attribute such effects to Open Access publications, neither would they constitute a 'key impact'.

Figure 4-4 Key Impact Pathway for Gold and Hybrid Open Access

Figure 4-4 represents the Key Impact Pathway identified for Gold and Hybrid Open access publications. From our analysis it emerged that both Gold and Hybrid Open Access positively affect citation and readership. For example, Gold Open Access manuscripts experience significantly higher Altmetric scores than closed ones (Long et al., 2022). However, citation advantage appears to vary according to discipline; for instance, in the humanities Open Access seems to benefit more from higher citation rates, compared to science (Dorta-González and Dorta-González, 2022). At the same time, within individual scientific fields, positive effects are also observed. In radiology, for example, Open Access articles have been shown to have higher citation rate, downloads, and shares than subscription-based articles (Alkhawtani et al., 2020).

An important consideration is the role of Open Access in supporting reproducibility. While being Open Access does not guarantee that a paper is reproducible, it removes access barriers that can limit who can read and evaluate the research outputs. Evidence from the literature suggests that OA publications are accessed and cited more frequently (Vadhera et al., 2022). This increased visibility is often argued to contribute indirectly to reproducibility by enabling a wider

audience of researchers to read the publications, assess the findings, and attempt replications. Therefore, while Open Access is a not guarantee of reproducibility, it creates the conditions under which reproducible research can be easily accessed and examined by researchers

Concerning academic impact, we found some potential negative effects on equity. Specifically, the hybrid market could generate inequity as some authors are able to pay APC while others are not. This inequity in publishing opportunity might also contribute to broader systemic inequalities by affecting the possibilities of some authors to contribute to knowledge production and dissemination.

Additionally, a study focused on the difference in citation rate between open access and subscription access articles in the field of radiology, showed that, in this specific field, articles from Europe or North America were more likely to be published Open Access compared to articles from Asia (Vadhera et al., 2022). This highlights an academic imbalance in publishing opportunities, which may also reflect broader societal differences in access to research outputs.

Open Access can also lead to wider dissemination of sensitive data such as images of patients, especially if ethics and consent procedures are not followed sufficiently. This could create a threat to privacy, particularly when dealing with health and patient-related data (Marshall et al., 2018).

In terms of economic impact, a positive correlation between APC and high impact journals was observed (Björk and Solomon, 2014). However, there are possible negative effects due to cost associated with APC. The hybrid market is also seen as dysfunctional because not everyone pays APC, and some authors pay both subscription fees and APC. On the other hand, there is a positive effect for readers, as they can freely access research without incurring costs. Furthermore, there seems to be a connection between Open Access and innovation. Open Access fosters knowledge sharing, which enhances collaboration between industry and academia, hence positively impacting innovation (Jong and Slavova, 2014), as evidence from non-patent literature in patents suggests.

The next step envisaged going through the same process for Green Open Access publications. Figure 4-5 shows a representation of the final pathway.

In terms of academic impact, Green Open Access appears to confer a greater **citation advantage** than Gold Open Access. For instance, one study comparing the citation impact of Green and Gold Open Access found that articles deposited in institutional repositories received over 106% more citations than those published in Gold OA or non-Open Access (Young and Brandes, 2020). Further evidence supporting the citation advantage of Green OA comes from studies on preprints deposited in repositories such as BioRxiv and ArXiv. Articles deposited on

these platforms showed higher citation rate and greater visibility than those not deposited. A possible explanation for this trend is the early availability of these preprinted articles, which allows researchers to cite them earlier, hence amplifying their citation impact. Articles with preprints uploaded to ArXiv received 35% higher citations compared to those that were not deposited (Davis and Fromerth, 2007).

Figure 4-5 Key Impact Pathway for Green Open Access

One factor at play is a potential quality bias, which suggests that more senior authors are more inclined to upload their work on ArXiv. As these authors often produce higher-quality research, their work is more likely to be cited. This could amplify the perceived citation impact of the deposited articles (Moed, 2007). Additionally, the citation advantage appears to be greater for disciplinary repositories compared to institutional repositories.

Nonetheless, when examining the impact at the manuscript level, the advantages of Green OA are less pronounced compared to Gold OA. While Gold OA manuscripts showed a significant

advantage in terms of visibility compared to closed-access publications, the difference in citation and visibility impact between Green OA manuscripts and closed-access is more limited (Long et al., 2022).

Despite its advantages, some types of Green OA, particularly preprinting, are associated with certain risks, particularly concerning the lack of peer review. The absence of peer review raises concerns regarding the quality of the papers, impacting trust and reliability. This became evident particularly during COVID-19, when the dissemination of problematic preprints potentially fuelled misinformation (Besançon et al., 2021).

Green Open Access tends to be less costly for authors than Gold or Hybrid models while benefiting accessibility and potential re-use of knowledge. While Green Open Access requires investments in infrastructure, it does not require authors or institutions to pay the article processing charges often associated with Gold OA. Therefore, Green OA can lower costs both for institutions and readers.

In terms of other benefits derived from openly accessible research publications, several articles highlighted benefits such as wider **readership**. For instance, one study (Tang et al., 2017) highlights how OA can facilitate the dissemination of research findings, making them more accessible to diverse stakeholders and communities. This increased accessibility aligns with the broader objectives of the **Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)** investigated by PathOS, particularly those related to education (SDG 4), health (SDG 3), gender equality (SDG 5), and environmental sustainability (SDG 13). By enhancing the availability of scholarly information, OA contributes to advancing knowledge and innovation, ultimately supporting efforts towards achieving the SDGs. Therefore, recognizing the potential positive impacts of OA on SDG-related outcomes adds another dimension to understanding its broader societal benefits. However, it is important to acknowledge that while OA may have the potential to contribute to the SDGs through facilitation of reuse and reduction of access cost and time, its actual impact in contributing to SDGs may vary depending on the individual SDGs contextual factors and implementation strategies.

Although it is difficult to identify long-term impacts of OA, the positive effects seen on **cost reduction**, especially for Green Open Access, increased **productivity**, and enhanced **efficiency** suggest significant potential (see chapter 4.1.3). Additionally, the increased availability of knowledge has fostered more **collaboration**, which in turn drives **innovation**. Furthermore, by making research outputs easily accessible, OA has the potential to maximise the effectiveness of R&D (Fell, 2019). Through these mechanisms, Open Access could also contribute to **economic growth**, although more research is required to confirm such links.

4.1.1. Discussion

While the presented Key Impact Pathways provide insights into the academic, economic, and societal benefits of Open Access publishing, critical limitations of this approach must be considered when evaluating the impact of Open Access. One significant factor is the **variation in OA effects and practices across different academic disciplines**. Research suggests that some academic fields experience higher citations and visibility on social media due to OA, while others, such as medicine and health sciences, do not show the same trend (Dorta-González and Dorta-González, 2022). This variability underscores the need to acknowledge the **influence of disciplinary contexts** when assessing the impact of OA on citation rates. In addition, even though OA increases readership overall, the quality of papers is still a crucial factor for citation patterns; high-quality papers are more likely to receive additional citations, while lower-quality papers available in Open Access may still be uncited after being read.

Though we analysed literature on **OA books**, due to the limited availability of data, we decided not to develop a separate pathway. However, key findings emerged. For instance, OA books tend to have higher media visibility than non-OA books, hence enhancing knowledge distribution, but with differences across disciplines (Wei and Noroozi Chakoli, 2020). The greater visibility, though, appears not to be correlated with greater academic citation rate (Wei and Noroozi Chakoli, 2020). A study revisiting a previous assessment of the impact of OA on books found that there is a slight positive correlation between OA, citations and tweets. However, language and discipline of the books played a key role in whether the books had social media engagement, with books in English (31%) and books in the humanities (22%) receiving higher engagement on social media (Snijder, 2016). Beyond academic influence, OA books also have economic implications. Readers can benefit from access free of charge. However, the production costs for a book are substantial.

Finally, the **costs of Open Access publishing** are a key item of current discourse on Open Access, be it through the lens of equity, APCs prohibiting different strata of researchers from publishing, or through financial sustainability of institutions being able to pay for publication costs. This study was not designed to comprehensively quantify all such financial costs and benefits of different Open Access publishing models and their effects on the publishing system (Tsipouri et al., 2025). Limited availability of data on publication costs and difficult-to-quantify effects of different publishing models on equity or general societal benefits remain a challenge that requires further work.

4.1.2. Indicators and metrics

The PathOS Open Science Indicator Handbook provides quantitative and qualitative indicators that can be used in monitoring and measuring the impacts of Open Science. The selection below presents the indicators that can be relevant for the impact of Open Access practices. They can be used as starting points to elaborate case-specific monitoring systems.

STEP	NAME	POSSIBLE INDICATORS/METRICS
Input	Different OA activities	APC Costs Availability of preprint repositories Availability of publication repositories Transformative publishing agreements
Output	Availability of Gold, Hybrid and Green Open Access publications	Distribution of Open Access journal models Prevalence of Open Access publishing
	Availability of OA books	Prevalence of preprinting
Outcome	Citations	Citation Impact
	Collaboration	Collaboration intensity Science-industry collaboration
	Efficiency	n/a
	Reproducibility	Reproducibility
	Trust	Uptake in and impact on societal issues
	Re-use and Uptake of research results by industry and other societal actors	Uptake in and impact on to societal issues Uptake in the legal sector
	Readership	Readership impact
Short-term impact	Quality	Quality
	Equity	Diversity
	Costs	Cost savings
	Innovation	Innovation output
	Productivity	n/a
	Policy and Governance	Uptake by policy makers
Long-term impact	Economic growth	Economic growth of companies
	SDGs	Uptake by patient groups Uptake in education Uptake in medical practice
	Labour market impact	Labour market impact of OS

4.1.3. Case study

Repositórios Científicos de Acesso Aberto de Portugal (RCAAP)

RCAAP (Repositório Científico de Acesso Aberto de Portugal), the Portugal Open Access Science Repository, is the central system to discover, locate and retrieve scientific content, including hundreds of thousands of publications, theses, conference proceedings, journal articles, and data, hosted in Portuguese institutional repositories. Its main objectives are to increase the visibility, accessibility and dissemination of Portuguese research results; facilitate access to information regarding these outputs; and integrate Portugal into a range of international initiatives for Open Access (OA). It is operated at the central level by the University of Minho and by the Foundation for National Scientific Computing (FCCN) – the digital unit of the national research funding agency of Portugal (FCT).

As main inputs we can identify the funding that secures running and maintaining the infrastructure and operation; the skilled staff from RCAAP and Portuguese institutions; the Portuguese legislation, mandating the deposit of master dissertations and PhD theses in

institutional repositories; and FCT's OA mandate, dating May 14th, 2014, making the self-archive of publications financed by this funder in a RCAAP-indexed repository compulsory.

The Development and Maintenance of the RCAAP Central System (Portal, Hosting Services, and Support Services) involves the technical work of building, updating, and maintaining the core infrastructure of RCAAP, which includes the central Portal for users and centralised repositories where content is stored. Ongoing maintenance and upgrading (e.g., moving to new versions of DSpace) ensures the continuity and improvement of the service. The Customisation, Operation, and Maintenance of Individual Repositories tailors the individual repositories to the specific needs of each institution. Definition and Updating of Individual Repository Policies ensure that technical and organisational aspects are well aligned, including content curation, data protection, and document submission policies for each repository. The Dissemination and Training and Helpdesk support the community of users, mainly repository managers.

The main outputs are the increased availability of repositories in Portugal and hence, of the accessibility and visibility of Portuguese scientific publications; this also allows for a better monitoring and tracking of publications by the Portuguese institutions and facilitated internal management at the institutional level. The support given by the helpdesk team and the training platform and materials can also be considered outputs and allow for a better quality of the information and better use of the RCAAP infrastructure.

This leads to short-term outcomes, such as the reduction of costs and time due to mutualization of efforts, an increased audience of Portuguese research outputs, increased learning and awareness opportunities, the development of new research and, possibly, new entrepreneurial ideas, as publications are more visible and accessible. Long-term outcomes can be an enhanced efficiency and productivity of Portuguese institutions, improved research and education, collaborations between academia and industry and cultural benefits to the wider society.

Lastly, possible impacts are the improvement in the state and functioning of the academic sector in Portugal, an increased level of innovation and the development of new solutions to address societal and public sector challenges.

4.2. Open and FAIR research data

Open data refers to data that can be freely accessed, reused, and redistributed by anyone.⁸ Data is considered open when it is available in its entirety to all users at no cost and when it is provided in a format that facilitates reuse and modification. **FAIR data**, on the other hand, is

⁸ <https://opendatahandbook.org/guide/en/what-is-open-data/>

To enhance clarity and coherence of the complex relationships between the codes, the initial mapping was simplified by renaming, merging, and adjusting different codes while preserving the underlying concepts. These adjustments followed an inductive approach and aimed to improve and streamline the representation of different types of impact chains, making the pathway more intuitive while ensuring that key dimensions remained distinguishable.

For instance, the initial code "Creation of new companies" was renamed "Labour market impacts" to encompass a wider range of labour-market outcomes beyond business formation. Similarly, "Policy and governance" was adjusted to "Behavioural change," capturing the broader shifts in institutional and individual practices influenced by open data. To further simplify and group limited occurrence in the data, "Climate/Environment" was merged into "SDG solutions," grouping sustainability-related benefits under the broader umbrella of societal challenges addressed by the Sustainable Development Goals.

Other refinements involved merging nodes that captured closely related concepts. For example, "Re-use of data in research" was integrated into the broader "Re-use" category, reflecting the diverse ways in which open data is repurposed across disciplines and sectors. Similarly, "Re-use and absorption of academic knowledge by societal actors" was combined with "Uptake of research results by societal actors,". In cases where concepts overlapped, a single term was retained; for instance, "Patenting" was merged with "Innovation,". Likewise, "Empowerment" and "Engagement" were grouped under "Behavioural change". Finally, "Science-industry collaboration" was consolidated into "collaboration".

4.2.2. Key impact pathway

After the simplification of the initial findings, the pathway was discussed and validated together with the PathOS consortium and structured in the form of an impact pathway which emanates from different activities under the umbrella of Open and FAIR data activities (Figure 4-7).

Figure 4-7 Key Impact Pathway for Open and FAIR Data

The findings from the sources reviewed highlight several **academic impacts** of Open and FAIR research data, particularly in terms of **reuse, reproducibility, trust, and citations**. Several articles illustrated how the availability of Open and FAIR data leads to an increase in **re-use** across different research fields. For instance, the COVID-19 Data Portal facilitated rapid access to data during the pandemic, leading to over 4 million visits and accelerating research efforts (Harrison et al., 2021). Similarly, studies on Landsat data (Michael et al. 2022) and the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) (Khan et al. 2021) show that open data policies significantly boosted dataset re-use, with biodiversity datasets increasingly cited in scientific literature.

The sources also highlight a **citation advantage** associated with open data. Research on gene expression microarray data found that studies sharing datasets received 9% more citations (Piwowar and Vision, 2013). Similarly, an analysis of medical image computing papers showed a 60% higher citation rate for studies using open data compared to those using private datasets (Heller et al., 2019). In addition, findings from the Environmental Data Initiative indicate that long-term datasets are more frequently cited than short-term ones (Gries et al., 2023).

Regarding **trust**, while the findings are nuanced, they ultimately point to a positive trend. Open data fosters transparency, enabling verification of research findings and reducing concerns about selective reporting. Suggesting that high-quality research is more likely to be openly shared, reinforcing trust in published results (Spiegelman, 2021). Furthermore, studies on data

reuse in the natural sciences indicate that researchers tend to rely on established repositories and known institutions as trusted data sources (Bishop and Collier, 2022). Although some challenges remain, such as variation in data quality and infrastructure gaps, open data generally enhances trust in scientific findings by providing a mechanism for validation and accountability.

The effect of open data on **research quality** tends to be mainly positive. Studies show, for instance, improved reporting in journals with data sharing policies (Nguyen et al., 2022). However, there are potential risks related to research quality as well. For example inflated error rates might occur from repeated statistical testing on the same datasets (Thompson et al., 2020). While high-quality research is more likely to be associated with data sharing, ensuring data curation remain critical for the effects on quality.

In relation to **economic impact**, Open Data can enhance productivity and efficiency by reducing duplication and facilitating broader access to scientific findings, reducing costs (Cole et al., 2023). The availability of Open and FAIR data is also shown to lead to increased collaboration with industry allowing industry to access scientific data (Tsipouri et al., 2025). The UniProt case study conducted by PathOS also confirms many economic benefits of Open Data practices (see Chapter 4.2.5).

The **societal impact** identified in the sources related to Open and FAIR data are seen particularly through health and environmental research. In healthcare, FAIR data has enabled predictive modelling to improve patient care, such as the FAIR4Health project, which used federated machine learning to predict hospital readmissions (Alvarez-Romero et al., 2022). Similarly, open data played a crucial role in the COVID-19 response by facilitating rapid access to research (Harrison et al., 2021).

In environmental science, Open and FAIR data support better policy decisions and sustainability efforts. For example, open-access databases have improved fisheries management (McManamay and Utz, 2014) while biodiversity platforms help track climate and ecological changes.

4.2.1. Discussion

While the presented Key Impact Pathway provides insights into the academic, economic, and societal benefits of Open and FAIR data practices, several limitations must be acknowledged. First, the approach primarily captures **measurable outputs and outcomes such as reuse, citations, and cost savings**, but it does not yet fully reflect more **complex qualitative aspects** like ethical considerations, as well as shifts in disciplinary norms. Ethical concerns, such as privacy risks and potential misuses of open data, are widely debated yet difficult to quantify in

citation or reuse metrics (Bezuidenhout and Chakauya, 2018). Furthermore, while open data is often associated with enhanced research transparency and increased trust, these **effects vary depending on the context** and stakeholders involved (McGillivray et al., 2022). Some studies indicate that although open data policies lead to citation advantages, the effect may diminish over time and is not uniform across disciplines (Christensen et al., 2019).

Beyond academic impacts, economically, open data facilitates **collaboration with industry, improving productivity and reducing inefficiencies** (Catalano et al. 2025). However, industry adoption of FAIR data practices appears in early stages and may require investments in skills development and infrastructure (Van Vlijmen et al., 2020). Cost-benefit assessments of the effects of data sharing remain premature and offer a complex picture where an initial investment in Open and FAIR Data infrastructure, stewardship, training and curation lead to an increase in costs but can later result in cost savings due to efficiency gains (Catalano et al., 2025). Societally, open data has been instrumental in fields such as health and climate research, such as in the case of the COVID-19 Data (Harrison et al., 2021). Yet, challenges persist, including disparities in access, where lower-income regions face infrastructural constraints limiting effective data use and reuse (Boudreau, 2021). While open data fosters innovation and contributes to SDG-related solutions, its benefits are not universally distributed, requiring ongoing policy and infrastructural support to bridge existing gaps.

4.2.2. Indicators and metrics

The PathOS Open Science Indicator Handbook provides quantitative and qualitative indicators that can be used in monitoring and measuring the impacts of Open Science. The selection below presents the indicators that can be relevant for the impact of Open and FAIR data practices. They can be used as starting points to elaborate case-specific monitoring systems.

STEP	NAME	POSSIBLE INDICATORS/METRICS
Input	Different Open and FAIR data activities	
Output	Availability of Open and FAIR Data Availability of Open platforms	Number/share of publications with Open Source code Number of data repositories Level of FAIRness of data Availability of data statement
Outcome	Re-use	Uptake in and impact on to societal issues Uptake in the legal sector
	Reproducibility	Reproducibility

	Collaboration	Collaboration intensity Science-industry collaboration
	Quality	Quality
Short-term impact	Costs	Cost savings
	Uptake of research results by industry and societal actors	Uptake in the legal sector Uptake in and impact on to societal issues
	Trust	n/a
	Citations	Citation Impact
Long-term impact	Labour market impacts	New Open Science skills and competences Number of new job positions
	Innovation	Innovation output
	Economic growth	Economic growth of companies
	SDGs	Uptake by patient groups Uptake in education Uptake in medical practice

4.2.3. Case study

UniProt

PathOS has carried out six targeted case studies to drive the modelling of impact pathways and to support testing and operationalization of Open Science indicators. To illustrate the impacts derived from Open and FAIR research data, one of these features a cost-benefit analysis (CBA) conducted on the UniProt resource. This example originates from the Bioinformatics case study and contributes to unravelling its impact pathway. It is particularly relevant to understanding the broader impacts of Open Science practices.

UniProt (Universal Protein Resource)⁹ is a comprehensive and freely accessible knowledgebase that provides protein sequence data and functional information. It serves as a critical resource for researchers in life sciences, providing high-quality annotations, sequences, and functional insights into proteins. UniProt integrates data from various sources, including experimental studies and computational predictions, to support advancements in biomedical research, drug discovery, and biotechnology. Additionally,

⁹ <https://www.uniprot.org/>

4.3. Citizen Science

Citizen Science refers to a diversity of collaborative approaches to scientific research that directly involve members of the public in the research processes. Approaches may range from

the public contribution of data through digital crowdsourcing, to full inclusion of members of the public in all aspects of research, from design, through execution, and dissemination. Approaches may be top-down, initiated by research teams or civil society organizations, or bottom-up, community-driven initiatives that respond to a problem or a need identified by a community. UNESCO considers Citizen Science an Open Science practice that facilitates the “open engagement of societal actors” in scientific research (UNESCO, 2021).

The European Commission frames Citizen Science as an essential practice for achieving the EU Missions through the Horizon Europe Framework Programme and it mentions Citizen Science as part of two Key Impact Pathways that form the assessment framework for Horizon Europe.¹⁰ Per the Commission, Citizen Science should help to achieve KIP 3: Fostering the diffusion of knowledge and open science and KIP 6: Strengthening the uptake of research and innovation in society. Within the latter, the number of Horizon Europe projects that involve citizens in co-creation of research and innovation is an indicator of short-term impact, number of initiatives with ongoing involvements of citizens after project completion as a medium-term impact indicator, and the uptake and dissemination of co-created research and innovation as a long-term indicator. Beyond Europe, the OECD reports that Citizen Science as a practice has increased tremendously since the early 2000s (as measured by share of publications that have “citizen science” in the title, abstract or keywords), and Citizen Science is referenced in several hundred science, technology and innovation policy instruments (European Commission et al., 2022).

The evidence of a policy focus on Citizen Science and related approaches indicates that governments believe that Citizen Science is critical to achieving their policy missions. Indeed, evidence suggests that Citizen Science can facilitate a range of impacts that support the achievement of a variety of sustainable development goals. A recent review study found that Citizen Science projects facilitate societal impacts in areas related to climate and environment, policy and governance, equity and empowerment, and health. Additionally, they support the democratization of scientific knowledge and process by fostering topics learning outcomes and research skill development (Cole et al. 2024). Another recent review found considerable evidence that Citizen Science supports research and innovation by increasing the “temporal and spatial scales of monitoring activities” within ecological and environmental research, and by diversifying the perspectives brought to bear on the scientific process (Klebel et al., 2025).

¹⁰ See https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/eu-missions-horizon-europe/eu-missions-and-citizen-engagement-activities_en

4.3.1. Pathway mapping

For this report, the downstream effects of **Citizen Science** practices were identified based on a “**downstream analysis**”. That is, the pathway was constructed starting with the selection of citizen science as the origin point. Resulting from activities related to citizen science are specific outputs, which in turn lead to outcomes and impacts.

Following the process outlined in chapter 2, an initial mapping based on the selected data is shown in Figure 4-8. The mapping shows the range of effects found to emanate from Citizen Science interventions. Prominently, the literature suggests that this leads to outputs such as availability of Open and FAIR data, people participating in CS projects, as well as collaboration with societal actors. At the outcome level, tangible outputs such as open and FAIR data enables re-use by different actors and, if curated properly, improves reproducibility. Research data sharing also enhances efficiency.

Academic effects may include novelty, in the sense that CS collaborations can encourage novel questions and approaches. Through the participation and collaborative aspects, societal effects such as education and awareness, behavioural change, and societal engagement are promoted. In fact, the added value of citizen science projects for participating citizen scientists is often understood as a principle of CS projects.¹¹

¹¹ See e.g., https://www.schweizforscht.ch/images/Swiss_CS_Principles/Swiss_CS_Principles.pdf

Figure 4-8 Initial mapping for citizen science

From the perspective of the study team, Visual 1 also includes several effects which can be understood as less relevant in the context of citizen science impacts, because they would only occur indirectly through the availability of FAIR data. Effects in the economic realm such as creation of new companies, increase in relevant products and services, labour market impacts, and tax revenue are likely not the focus of Citizen Science projects nor always attributable to them. They also did not feature in the source documents addressing Citizen Science, but in those looking at the creation of Open/FAIR data in the context of typical research projects. Therefore, they were summarised in the eventual pathway under broad potential economic impacts following discussion among the study team.

4.3.2. Key impact pathway

The next step taken by the research team was to simplify and refine the mapping to improve its clarity and make it easier to understand.

Figure 4-9 presents the recast pathway. As explained above, economic impacts were grouped together. The effects illustrated in this figure are related to outputs of Citizen Science projects, in particular, availability of data, the participation of people, as well as collaborations related to

the Citizen Science project. The availability of open and FAIR data enables academic effects, including the **re-use of data, productivity, efficiency**, as well as **quality**, and, as explained above, **novelty**. Open data also relates citizen science to **reproducibility**. Many of these outcomes have the potential to create economic impacts, for example through **cost savings** or improved **governance**. Yet, the specific evidence is limited and therefore the illustration does not draw a direct connection to the long-term economic impacts of Citizen Science.

Figure 4-9 Key Impact Pathway for Citizen Science

Figure 4-8 further illustrates that societal effects are created through the **participants** experience in projects and the societal collaboration around SC activities. The evidence has shown that **participation** in citizen science and **collaboration** can create stronger **societal participation**, lead to **empowerment** of citizen scientists, improve **education and awareness** of certain issues, as well as societal **engagement**. These together, sometimes in correlation with the improved data quality, can lead to effects on policy and governance, if conditions permit so. Changed **policy and governance** can in turn lead to impact on the sustainable development goals at large or in more concrete areas such as **health** and **environment** (see also chapter 4.7).

4.3.1. Discussion

While the presented Key Impact Pathways provide insights into the academic, economic, and societal benefits of Open Access publishing, critical limitations of this approach must be considered when evaluating the impact of Open Access.

Citizen Science impacts are often societal in nature and the result of complex processes and dynamics. The analysis of publications focussing on Citizen Science highlights these contextual factors of Citizen Science which can affect the realisation of impacts. They also illustrate important underlying assumptions and potential limitations of the pathway.

A main finding concerned the quality of data resulting from Citizen Science projects. Some studies argue that data quality may be affected by demographic factors such as age and level of education. Therefore, to have a successful citizen science project which produces high-quality research data, it is important that the project and the participant expectations are closely aligned (Earp et al., 2020). A key factor impacting data quality is training. Thus, providing training to the citizens undertaking the projects can be a key for obtaining sound data (Ratnieks et al., 2016). Yet other studies found no significant quality discrepancy between data collected by citizens or by experts (see e.g. Crall et al., 2011). Investment in training also mean higher costs, which may offset financial savings incurred through participatory projects.

Clear benefits can be found for the participating citizens: participating did not only positively impact the participants' knowledge and attitude towards science (Bruckermann et al., 2021), but it improved also their soft skills such as communication, as well as argumentation and critical thinking skills (Araujo et al., 2022). Furthermore, participation in Citizen Science projects provoked "a desire to make a difference" (Walker et al., 2021), a feeling of satisfaction and enjoyment in the participants for contributing to science.

Yet, there are several aspects that limit the potential effects. Some projects may experience accessibility issues due to the way in which they are planned and conducted. For instance, if they require physical tasks or intensive activities, this may limit participation (Earp et al., 2020). Additional factors potentially hindering participation in CS projects are linked to geographic and social bias which may occur due to CS projects being mostly carried out in North America or Europe and in which participants are middle-class and have access to education (Walker et al., 2021). In addition, another potential limiting factor of CS is the frequent requirement of using technological tools, which are not always available to all members of the society (Walker et al., 2021).

Participants' motivation can also be a challenge to the scientists in the project, namely, to maintain the motivation of the volunteers to continue contributing to the project. Feedback and social recognition were found to play a pivotal role in keeping the interest and motivation high. The greater they are, the more participants are inclined to contribute to CS (Earp et al., 2020).

In terms of challenges, achieving policy and governance impact represents a major one; while there is evidence of CS having an impact at local and regional levels, and being used as an instrument for monitoring environmental and health related issues, evidence of CS impact at national and international levels is limited (Klebel et al., 2023). One reason for this may be the difficulty in acknowledging CS data as scientific evidence by policymakers (Mahajan et al., 2022). In some understandings of CS, impact on policy is a secondary objective after the goal to answer scientific questions.¹² Thus, balancing expectations about scientific impact and societal or other impacts derived from CS actions is important.

It should also be mentioned that implementing Citizen Science projects can be associated with potential risks. For example, there can be health and safety risks to participants arising from CS. Several studies highlighted that projects might expose participants to dangerous situations, for instance, while collecting data on floods (Walker et al., 2021). In addition, Citizen science projects often encompass the use of technological tools which may contain personal information of the participants, and which must be treated carefully (Walker et al., 2021). Therefore, ill-designed projects may threaten the privacy of participants' data.

4.3.2. Indicators and metrics

The PathOS Open Science Indicator Handbook provides quantitative and qualitative indicators that can be used in monitoring and measuring the impacts of Open Science. The selection below presents the indicators that can be relevant for CS activities.

STEP	NAME	POSSIBLE INDICATORS/METRICS
Input	Citizen science	Citizen Science indicators (OS)
Output	Availability of Open and FAIR Data	Level of FAIRness of data Availability of data statement Deposition of Open Metadata Prevalence of open/FAIR data practices
	Societal collaborations	Extra-academic collaborations
	Engagement	Citizen Science indicators (OS)

¹² https://www.schweizforscht.ch/images/Swiss_CS_Principles/Swiss_CS_Principles.pdf

	Number of people participating in CS projects	Citizen Science indicators (OS)
Outcome	Education and awareness	Scientific literacy
	Empowerment	Uptake in and impact on societal issues
	Collaboration	Collaboration intensity Science-industry collaboration
	Efficiency	Reuse of data in research
	Reproducibility	Reproducibility
	Re-use and Uptake of research results by industry and other societal actors	Uptake in and impact on to societal issues Uptake in the legal sector Uptake in education Uptake by patient groups Uptake in medical practice
	Citations	Citation Impact
	Novelty	Interdisciplinary and novelty
Short-term impact	Quality	Quality
	Equity	Diversity
	Costs	Cost savings
	Innovation	Innovation output
	Productivity	n/a
	Policy and Governance	Uptake by policy makers
Long-term impact	Economic growth	Economic growth of companies
	SDGs	Uptake in and impact on societal issues Socially relevant products and processes

4.4. Open code and software

Open code and open source software (OSS) refers to software for which the source code is made freely available for use, modification, and redistribution under permissive licensing terms.¹³ Understanding the potential societal, economic, and academic impacts of Open-Source Software (OSS) is of growing interest, as OSS has the potential to play an increasingly prominent role in research and innovation ecosystems. The development, sharing, and use of code and software may be linked to a range of effects, including enabling collaboration, supporting the reproducibility of research, reducing development costs, and contributing to the creation of new products and services. code and software may also have broader implications for

¹³https://commission.europa.eu/about/departments-and-executive-agencies/digital-services/open-source-strategy-history_en

knowledge dissemination, skills development, and the uptake and reuse of research outputs by societal and economic actors. In the following sections, we draw on evidence collected through the literature review conducted within the PathOS project to illustrate how the development, sharing, and use of open-source software can create academic, societal, and economic impacts.

4.4.1. Pathway mapping

For this report, effects of Open-source software practices were identified based on a “downstream analysis”, i.e., the analysis started with specific interventions related to Open-source software before identifying their associated effects and impacts.

Visualising the coded effects in the corpus (Figure 4-10) reveals a significant set of connections between open-source software interventions and various outputs, outcomes, and impacts. In total, seven instances of “Open code/software” were coded in the corpus, highlighting this as a relatively underexplored area. The effects of activities tagged as “Open code/software” in the literature review were found to link not just to outputs in terms of “Availability of open code/software” (3 instances), but also to “Open/FAIR Data” and the “Availability of open platforms”, which act as key enablers for downstream effects. The co-occurrence of open code/software with these other outputs implies that code and software are not isolated outputs but often created in projects and initiatives which generate data outputs or platforms that relate to code and software.

These outputs connect to outcomes including “Reuse and absorption of academic knowledge by societal actors” (14), “Uptake of research results by industry” (7), and “Engagement” (7), alongside improvements in “Efficiency” (6) and “Cost savings” (14). Such outcomes reflect how open software fosters more efficient research practices and facilitates greater diffusion of research results to non-academic actors.

Further downstream, the coded outcomes relate to short-term impacts such as “Productivity” (8), “Relevant products and services” (4), and “Policy and governance” (10), supporting a more innovation-driven and collaborative ecosystem. These, in turn, are associated with long-term economic impacts like “Labour market impacts” (4), “Economic growth” (5), and “Tax revenue” (5), as well as broader societal benefits like “SDG solutions” (16) and “Health” (11).

Figure 4-10 Initial Mapping for open code/software

The initial coding was followed by a simplification and consolidation of codes to improve the coherence of the pathway representation. “Re-use of data in research” and “Re-use and absorption of academic knowledge by economic actors” were merged under the broader “Re-use” and “Uptake of research results” categories to reflect diverse applications. “Creation of new companies” was grouped into “Labour market impacts,” and “Policy and governance” merged with “Behavioural change” to capture broader institutional effects. “Innovation,” “Cost savings,” and “Productivity” were retained as distinct nodes due to their frequent and specific occurrence. These adjustments followed an inductive approach to create a simplified yet relatable mapping of the causal relationships underpinning the use and impact of open-source software.

4.4.2. Key impact pathway

The findings from the reviewed literature highlight a range of academic, economic, and societal impacts linked to the development, sharing, and use of open-source software. Across the

sources, outcomes include increased **efficiency**, enhanced **reproducibility**, **collaboration**, and **cost-savings**, as well as subsequent effects such as **innovation** and societal responsiveness during emergencies.

Figure 4-11 Final Pathway for open code/software

The findings related to **academic impacts** suggest that open-source software (OSS) holds potential to generate a range of academic impacts. These include improved research efficiency through reduced time on routine tasks, as reported by users of open electronic laboratory notebooks (European Commission, 2019) and enhanced reproducibility and transparency through version control, audit trails, and public sharing of code and methods (Heumüller et al., 2020; McCormick et al., 2014). OSS also facilitates knowledge retention and collaborative development, particularly when paired with open data infrastructures (Reinertsen et al., 2021). In contexts with limited resources, OSS tools such as Open Data Kit (ODK) have enabled scalable, inclusive, and adaptable research data collection (Bokonda et al., 2019). Although some evidence suggests a modest citation advantage for publications sharing software artifacts (Heumüller et al., 2020), uptake remains limited due to barriers such as perceived complexity, lack of incentives, and concerns about code quality (European Commission, 2019). Nonetheless, OSS appears to be an enabler of Open Science aims, supporting reusability, transparency, and more sustainable academic research practices.

Economic impacts are mainly observed in terms of increased efficiency, reduced costs, and innovation facilitation. The Open Data Kit (ODK) framework, an open-source mobile data

collection tool, illustrates how OSS lowers operational costs in public health settings by eliminating licensing fees and allowing local adaptation (Bokonda et al., 2019). Similarly, Kobayashi et al. (2021) demonstrate how open software tools were used during the COVID-19 pandemic for epidemic modelling and information platforms, accelerating innovation in both the public and private sectors by enabling timely responses and reduced development overheads (Kobayashi et al., 2021).

Other research further notes that open-source tools are increasingly seen as complementary to proprietary technologies in R&D, particularly for small firms and academic spin-offs, facilitating product development and experimentation without the burden of upfront software investment (European Commission, 2019).

Societal impacts are seen particularly in crisis response, health, and education. For example, Kobayashi et al. (2021) highlight how civic tech initiatives using OSS helped deliver critical health information during the pandemic, thereby supporting governments and citizens alike. In addition, Bokonda et al. (2019) report that the deployment of open tools like ODK has strengthened health systems by improving the quality and timeliness of health data collection in low-resource contexts.

Moreover, open platforms like ITK and ODK contribute to broader **SDG-related outcomes** by enabling scalable, adaptable, and locally maintained digital solutions. While evidence of long-term societal impact is still emerging, the reviewed literature underscores OSS's value as an enabler of inclusive and responsive digital infrastructures.

In sum, open-source software enhances reproducibility, efficiency, and trust within academia, facilitates innovation and cost-reduction in industry, and supports socially responsive applications in health and governance especially in crisis and low-resource settings. These impacts are contingent upon sustained community engagement, interoperability, and recognition of software as a critical scholarly output.

4.4.3. Discussion

The impact pathway for open-source software (OSS) is constructed based on a limited set of available studies, many of which focus on individual cases. While these case studies suggest that open availability of source code can enhance accessibility, transparency, adaptability, and reuse of digital tools, the overall evidence base remains narrow and uneven. Findings are often drawn from specific domains such as public health, medical imaging, or environmental monitoring, and may not generalise across disciplines, regions, or types of OSS.

One key limitation is the difficulty of isolating the specific effects of OSS from those of other Open Science practices. In many instances, open software is created in projects which create open research data, use collaborative infrastructures, or Citizen Science approaches, making it challenging to attribute observed impacts to OSS alone.

Furthermore, few of the reviewed studies examine the long-term or systemic impacts of OSS in a rigorous manner. Most of the reported effects-such as improved reproducibility, efficiency, or user engagement-are proximate or intermediate outcomes, and the causal links to broader academic, societal, or economic impacts remain largely inferential. This limits the extent to which the pathway represents the higher-level impacts of open research software.

In addition, some emerging areas, such as the intersection of OSS and artificial intelligence, are only weakly represented in the literature, often due to the publication lag or the recency of these developments. As a result, potential impacts in these areas remain underexplored.

Finally, the effectiveness and uptake of open research software depend on several enabling factors, including the quality of documentation, ongoing community support, interoperability, and users' technical capacity. Without these, open research software may be difficult to adopt or sustain, especially in low-resource settings.

In summary, the presented impact pathway is a simplified representation of a complex and evolving landscape. It reflects the available evidence but should be interpreted with caution.

4.4.4. Indicators and metrics

The PathOS Open Science Indicator Handbook provides quantitative and qualitative indicators that can be used in monitoring and measuring the impacts of Open Science. The selection below presents the indicators that can be relevant for the monitoring of the input, outputs, outcomes and impact of Open and FAIR data practices. They can be used as starting points to elaborate case-specific monitoring systems.

STEP	NAME	POSSIBLE INDICATORS/METRICS
Input	Different open-source software activities	n/a
Output	Availability of Open and FAIR Data Availability of Open source software and platforms	Prevalence of Open Method practices Use of code in research Impact of Open Code in research Number of data repositories

		Level of FAIRness of data Availability of data statement
Outcome	Re-use	Uptake in and impact on to societal issues Uptake in the legal sector
	Reproducibility	Reproducibility
	Collaboration	Collaboration intensity Science-industry collaboration
	Quality	Quality
Short-term impact	Costs	Cost savings
	Uptake of research results by industry and societal actors	Uptake in the legal sector Uptake in and impact on to societal issues
	Trust	n/a
	Citations	Citation Impact
Long-term impact	Labour market impacts	New Open Science skills and competences Number of new job positions
	Innovation	Innovation output
	Economic growth	Economic growth of companies
	SDGs	Uptake by patient groups Uptake in education Uptake in medical practice

4.5. Environment

Under environmental impacts, we understand any wider effect which can be traced back to Open Science interventions which relates to the natural environment. These are likely to be indirect, such as through improving environmental policies and governance and monitoring. As a result, this describes more *potential* impacts rather than concrete, measurable effects. While theoretically possible, the direct effect of CS projects on the natural environment is not typically monitored (see e.g. Cole et al. 2024). Nonetheless, the impact pathway serves the purpose to showcase some mechanisms identified in literature through which Open Science practices could indirectly support benefits to the environment.

4.5.1. Pathway mapping

Error! Reference source not found. displays the initial mapping resulting of this exercise. Looking back from the impact “environment”, all preceding steps were identified. **Policy and governance, behavioural change, and equity** are identified factors promoting environmental benefits. Productivity also appeared, although only in a single instance.

Moving one step further, the mapping displays a connection between outcomes such as **education and awareness, participation, engagement, and societal collaborations**, which are supported by Citizen Science practices.

In addition, the **availability of Open/FAIR data** was found to connect to **empowerment**, and also to **policy and governance**. Open and FAIR data promote various economic effects, such as **cost savings, science-industry collaboration, and uptake of research results by industry**. These can have a positive effect on productivity. Here, however, it should be noted that such economic effects might also increase use of natural resources and thus have potentially detrimental effects on the environment.

Open access publications also show a weak link with policy and governance and the **reuse and absorption of academic knowledge**, which in turn connects to **behavioural change**, and empowerment. Many effects are interconnected, pointing to possible feedback loops and complicated causal links between these outcomes and possible impacts.

Figure 4-12 Initial mapping for environment

The preliminary mapping illustrates the important mediating factor of policy and governance, which can be affected by a broad range of societal aspects. In addition, the **availability of data**, such as collected through citizen science projects, can improve quality of decision-making, through better monitoring systems, but also empower societal actors to use such data to improve policy making. At the individual level, behavioural change is an outcome which can result from participation in citizen science activities.

4.5.2. Key impact pathway

The resulting Key Impact Pathway is displayed in **Error! Reference source not found.** Firstly, the impact on environment is displayed as a long-term effect, which is largely mediated through short-term impacts on policy and governance, as well as behavioural change. Other, less pronounced economic effects such as cost savings and productivity gains may also come to play, for example by reducing consumption of resources.

These, in turn, are affected by several intermediary outcomes. Relevant factors identified in the literature are the reuse and uptake of results (such as data, publications, monitoring frameworks). Besides the relevance of using outputs, societal processes and factor are at play. Notably, empowerment, engagement, and education and awareness can lead to behavioural change and policy and governance improvements. Due to the proximity of the concepts and

difficulty in isolating their effects at this level, they are clustered together in the pathway. Equity was found to have a link to policy and governance and to climate and environment, respectively. However, the causal relationship of the concept of equity to these impacts is likely complex.

At the output stage, the impact pathway highlights the availability of results in the form of publications and data sets. In addition, societal collaboration and the individual participants, for example in citizen science projects, cannot be forgotten. As avenues for influence at the political and personal level, individual agents of change and societal networks are crucial mechanisms to translate science into policy.

Figure 4-13 Key Impact Pathway for environment

4.5.3. Discussion

The screening of the literature showed that Open Science, and in particular Citizen Science, can result in impacts on the environment, particularly on biodiversity, pollution, conservation, etc. Yet, specific limitations relate to the question of direct and potential impacts, as well as the critical role of policy and governance. These are important mediating factors making it

challenging to attribute direct causal effects to Open Science practices and to generalise the findings.

For example, several studies found evidence of indirect impacts of involvement of participants in CS activities on the environment. CS enhanced participants' understanding of environmental topics and prompted the adoption of more environmentally friendly behaviour (Santori et al., 2021). In particular, a positive impact on participants' attitude towards animals, nature and biodiversity was observed (Kelemen-Finan et al., 2018).

In addition, it was found that CS increased availability of data, hence contributing to better monitoring and understanding of environmental issues. This, in turn, influenced engagement with policy making, thereby potentially affecting environment in long-term. For instance, Brooks et al. (2019) reported that a CS project was observed to complement the work of the public authorities, resulting in enhanced governmental monitoring of pollution, and enforcement of sanctions.

However, engaging with policymaking also poses challenges, as documented by Dhillon (2017) who found that CS activities boosted empowerment and community building, but encountered difficulties in influencing political decision-making, hence leading to limited impacts on policy making procedures.

In addition, as with the impact of CS displayed in the first pathway, the quality of data collected through CS projects, as well as the impact of participants is dependent on enabling factors such as training.

4.5.4. Indicators

STEP	NAME	RELATED INDICATORS/METRICS
Activity	Citizen Science activities	Citizen Science Indicators
	Open/FAIR data	Availability of data repositories
	Open Access policies and practices	Transformative publishing agreements
	Open Methods	Prevalence of Open Method practices
Output	Open code/software	Use of code in research
		Reuse of code in research
Output	Availability of Open/FAIR data	Deposition of Open Metadata

		Prevalence of open/FAIR data practices Reuse of data in research
Short-term impact	Availability of Open Access publications (Gold)	Prevalence of Open Access publishing
Long-term impact	Preregistrations	n/a
	Open Platforms	n/a
Outcome	Reproducibility	Inclusion in systematic reviews or meta-analyses
		Level of replication
		Polarity of publications
		Consistency in reported numbers
		Prevalence of replication studies

4.6. Reproducibility

Reproducibility is understood as the ability of a researcher to obtain same or similar results as those of a previous study by reusing the original data (Dudda et al. 2024). Assessing the impact of Open Science practices on reproducibility presents a significant challenge, as it is often difficult to establish clear, causal evidence linking specific actions to measurable improvements in this area. In this study, we aim to explore whether it is possible to identify specific activities which, when implemented, may contribute to enhanced reproducibility of research findings.

4.6.1. Pathway mapping

For this report, effects and impacts on **reproducibility** were identified based on an “**upstream analysis**”, i.e., the analysis started from a certain type of impact and identified the outcomes, outputs and interventions leading up to them.

Following the process outlined in chapter 2, the initial mapping for Reproducibility is shown in Figure 4-14. A few clarifications will help to interpret the graph: the colours used are purely aesthetic and carry no analytical meaning. In the figure, both the size of the nodes and the thickness of the connections are scaled to reflect the number of associated evidence items.

Figure 4-14 Initial mapping for reproducibility

As demonstrated in the initial mapping, the available evidence specifically addressing reproducibility remains limited. Nonetheless, it was possible to identify certain correlations that suggest which activities may influence reproducibility.

Beginning with the final outcome, **reproducibility**, all preceding steps were identified. Among the various Open Science practices examined, the **availability of Open/FAIR data** emerged as the primary factor most consistently associated with improved chances of reproducibility. This finding aligns with the widely held understanding that making research data FAIR enables other researchers to reuse data and attempt to replicate research findings.

In contrast, other Open Science activities, such as **Open Access publishing and open research platforms** appear less frequently as factors contributing to reproducibility. In the case of **Open Access** publishing, the access to scientific literature is of course a basic prerequisite for reproducibility of any kind, even if the publishing model does not affect scientific rigour and methodology. Journals also play a role, through the peer review function, as well as through promoting access to data underlying results. The single occurrence of **preregistration** appears

to reflect the small number of studies which were selected for the literature review. This should not be construed as evidence of limited importance but points to limitations of the available evidence and study design.

The mapping further clarified the specific inputs that contribute to these intermediate outputs, which may ultimately influence reproducibility. These inputs include **Open Access practices, Open/FAIR data policies, the sharing of Open Code/Software and Methods, and Citizen Science initiatives**. The overarching objective of this work is to provide a practical tool to support stakeholders in identifying which Open Science activities are most likely to enhance reproducibility.

4.6.2. Key impact pathway

Following the initial representation, the pathway was discussed and validated in collaboration with members of the PathOS consortium and was subsequently structured into an **impact pathway** that originates from various Open Science activities (see Figure 4-15).

Figure 4-15 Final pathway for Reproducibility

This emerging impact pathway represents the relationship between reproducibility as an outcome that can be supported by a range of individual open science practices. This includes preregistrations, open/FAIR data, or open platforms (e.g., electronic lab notebooks). In principle, these can be resulting from various interventions, including, for example citizen science

projects which create open or FAIR data. The relevance of open source code and software as an output was added as another step due to the occurrence in several identified activities.

One cited example is the use of **Electronic Laboratory Notebooks (ELNs)** (European Commission, 2019), a software used by researchers to organize and record scientific data. ELNs are recognized for their role in facilitating open data sharing and serving as data management tools that align with the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Re-usable). When properly implemented, they can contribute to more transparent and structured data practices, thus promoting reproducibility. However, their adoption remains limited due to factors such as usability challenges, cost, and accessibility.

In the already small selection of studies identified as addressing reproducibility, only a few reported evidence for the correlation between **Open Data policies and reproducibility**. One highlighted the indirect effects of data sharing policies in enhancing transparency and creating better conditions for independent verification and reproduction of research findings. One study, (Laurinavichyute et al., 2022), for example, examined the effects of introducing a mandatory data-sharing policy, comparing articles published before and after the policy was implemented. Although the study did not assess pre-policy reproducibility rates, the findings were notable: the introduction of the policy led to a more than 50% increase in data sharing among authors. Despite this, datasets associated with 8 of the 59 examined papers remained unavailable. The reproducibility rates following the implementation of the policy varied from 34% to 56%, contingent upon the criteria used. Notably, the study found that providing access to analysis code corresponded with a 40% increase in reproducibility, highlighting the critical contribution of code sharing to the reproducibility of research (Laurinavichyute et al., 2022).

Another example is provided by the Insight Toolkit (ITK), an **open-source software library** for medical image analysis. A case study on ITK highlights how transparency in methodologies, data, and code can actively foster reproducibility (McCormick et al., 2014). Beyond providing a platform the ITK community supports reproducibility through its scientific journal, the Insight Journal. This journal requires authors to submit comprehensive materials (code, datasets etc..) ensuring that published findings can be independently verified and built upon. The case study's authors argue that ITK has contributed to enhancing reproducibility within its field by strengthening core scientific practices. However, they also note that wider adoption of such practices across the research community remains limited and will likely require broader cultural and institutional change.

While **preregistration** was not reported to have a direct effect on reproducibility rates in the studies reviewed, a study (Bakker et al., 2020) suggested that it can still provide indirect

benefits. By improving both research transparency and data quality, preregistration may help foster conditions that support more reproducible and trustworthy research outcomes over time.

4.6.3. Discussion

It is important to acknowledge that the impact pathway constructed for reproducibility is informed by a relatively small and fragmented body of evidence, much of which is based on individual cases. While these cases offer valuable insights, especially regarding the positive effects of open data and code sharing, they also highlight a critical limitation: direct empirical evidence establishing a causal relationship between Open Science practices and improved reproducibility remains limited and inconclusive.

A central debate in the reproducibility literature is the recognition that making research outputs openly available does not automatically guarantee reproducibility. Reproducibility requires more than just access to data and code. It also depends on the availability of clear, detailed, and transparent reporting of research methods, protocols, and analytical procedures. Without such accompanying information, even openly shared datasets and code may fall short in enabling others to accurately reproduce research findings.

While open data sharing is widely recognized as a critical step toward increasing research transparency, the quality, completeness, and usability of shared datasets vary significantly. For example, an observational study (Hardwicke et al., 2018) assessed the reproducibility of results from 35 articles with available data. The findings revealed that data availability alone was insufficient to guarantee reproducibility: only a portion of results could be fully reproduced without contacting the authors, and even then, they were unable to reproduce all results. This highlights that, while open data is crucial for reproducibility, it is not sufficient on its own. Data curation, clear analysis scripts, and thorough documentation are also essential.

Additionally, open data policies may have unintended consequences that could inadvertently hinder reproducibility. Thompson et al. (2020) highlighted the risk of increased false positives resulting from excessive reuse of the same datasets. When multiple researchers repeatedly analyse the same dataset, the probability of finding false-positive results increases purely due to statistical chance. This highlights the need for careful interpretation of findings from highly reused datasets and points to the importance of good statistical practices and proper reporting when conducting replication efforts.

In addition, interventions which are not directly considered within the scope of Open Science are not reflected in the findings. For example, methodological training can be facilitated by

Open Science practices (open data, open software), and often incorporates them, but is not dependent on it. Further research on the effects of the interplay between reproducibility training and open science would be required to expand on the findings derived from the PathOS literature review.

To conclude, Open Science practices, particularly open data and code sharing, enhance transparency and accessibility and are thus enabling conditions for promoting reproducibility. They are not the only measures which can be taken. Additional measures, including better documentation, methodological transparency, and data curation, are essential to realize the full potential of Open Science in improving research reproducibility.

4.6.4. Indicators and metrics

The PathOS Open Science Indicator Handbook provides quantitative and qualitative indicators that can be used in monitoring and measuring the impacts of Open Science. The selection below presents the indicators that can be relevant to investigate reproducibility. They can be used as starting points to elaborate case-specific monitoring systems.

STEP	NAME	RELATED INDICATORS/METRICS
Activity	Citizen Science activities	Citizen Science Indicators
	Open/FAIR data	Availability of data repositories
	Open Access policies and practices	Transformative publishing agreements
	Open Methods	Prevalence of Open Method practices
Output	Open code/software	Use of code in research Reuse of code in research
Output	Availability of Open/FAIR data	Deposition of Open Metadata Prevalence of open/FAIR data practices Reuse of data in research
Short-term impact	Availability of Open Access publications (Gold)	Prevalence of Open Access publishing
Long-term impact	Preregistrations	n/a
	Open Platforms	n/a

Outcome	Reproducibility	Inclusion in systematic reviews or meta-analyses Level of replication Polarity of publications Consistency in reported numbers Prevalence of replication studies
---------	-----------------	--

5. Limitations of the approach and evidence

Studying the causal effects of Open Science practices is a challenging exercise. Within PathOS, this aspect has been addressed in different tasks. The results of a large-scale scoping review (Klebel et al., 2024) already highlighted that many of the screened academic studies did not support causal claims due to their study design. In addition, the scoping review illustrated that the role of confounding variables, due to data or conceptual issues, is difficult to assess and that effects and their size and strength are complicated to measure. It also found a risk of being subject to a “streetlight effect”, that is a specific observational bias related to the availability of data. Lessons learned about the study of Open Science impacts are summarised in PathOS Deliverable 1.4 ‘Validated model of Key OS Impact Pathways and guidelines/recommendations’ (forthcoming). These lessons learned capture limitations concerning the limited availability of evidence, methodological and conceptual issues.

The identified pathways reflect similar problems, such as bias towards the available and eventually selected evidence. For example, the underlying scoping reviews focused on the presence of certain notions of evidence for impacts in the literature, often in quantitative or at least metric terms. This does not reflect the variety of methods which can be used for policy evaluation, which includes experimental, statistical and indicator-based methods, but also systems analysis methods, and qualitative methods (see e.g. Reed et al. 2021).

However, the absence of evidence found in the literature does not mean that there is an absence of impacts or other effects. Neither does a frequent presence of a given effect or impact in the body of literature mean that the effect size is large. Rather, an abundance of evidence could be attributed to the streetlight effect or the ease of collecting, for instance, bibliometric data about citation effects or evaluations applied in citizen science projects. In addition, evidence for more recent practices may not yet have been available due to time-lags

of scientific publications as well as lack of evaluation reports for recent Open Science policy programmes and projects.

In addition, negative effects as well as confounding variables and effects are not necessarily represented in the impact chains either. Yet it is good practice to anticipate and explicate them during an intervention design, if not trying to find a remedy through the intervention design themselves. In this report, we addressed such known limitations through the discussion provided for each pathway.

In addition, Open Science is an umbrella term. The causal mechanism between the open availability of a data set and its reuse differs from the causal mechanism of a Citizen Science project leading to changes in policy and governance and by extension health and the environment. For example, the impact of open access on policy and governance may be constructed as the effect of the openness of articles on policymaking at large. Yet, the science-policy interface has been researched in many different contexts, and those results show that different mechanisms are at play, translating research results into policy (see e.g., Nelson et al. 2023). Developing a theoretically coherent concept for all individual causal mechanisms is out of the scope of the PathOS project. Yet, seeing the impact pathways as structural causal models (Klebel and Traag, 2024), without always implying the type and strength of effect, allows generalising the findings to a certain extent.

A further challenge derived from the approach taken in this task is the “cumulative” step in the identification of the impact pathways. The underlying assumption of this action is that certain outputs or outcomes will have similar effects, no matter the original focus of the intervention. For example, citation advantages of open access publications can occur also in projects that focussed on citizen science effects. Efficiency gains from re-use of data are not fundamentally different from efficiency gains in access costs for scientific publications, or re-use of codes.

Nonetheless, through the approach taken for this work, grouping of effects from different interventions using a similar code and then identifying impact chains independent from the original interventions means that the causal effect that may be identifiable in one case is not necessarily the same as in the next case with the same code and components. This level of granularity is lost with the design of the pathways and is a result of a trade-off between providing overarching pathways which showcase possibilities of impacts of Open Science and case-by-case impact chains with more detailed and reliable causal claims. This is notwithstanding the fact that the collecting robust evidence for population-level impacts outside the sphere of control and influence of individual interventions and their beneficiaries is always challenging.

With the intention to illustrate several key pathways to impacts of different Open Science interventions, this trade-off is taken by the PathOS project. The alternative would be to not have higher-level impact pathways that group and cumulate impacts at all. In practice, the step of simplifying the findings into pathways also includes a decision on reducing the total amount of components and steps in the individual pathways through the judgements by the project team and the validation with stakeholders. This is another source of potential bias.

The results of PathOS are increasingly pointing to the need for more empirical studies with study designs addressing causal effects. PathOS aims to inspire such studies in the context of the project's case studies. It is also the intention of PathOS to inspire future academic research as well as practical studies, for example impact assessments and evaluations in a policy context, by identifying gaps of evidence or causal understanding of the effects of Open Science practices and resources.

6. Conclusions

This report set out to identify and illustrate Key Impact Pathways of Open Science practices. In this updated report, six Key Impact Pathways are presented, following a thorough revision of the original deliverable and adjustments to the approach underlying the first version (Karasz et al., 2024). Each Key Impact Pathway is enriched with contextual information and a brief discussion of limitations – and, for practitioners, with potential indicators from the PathOS Open Science Indicator Handbook.

The resulting Key Impact Pathways highlight the diversity of impacts created by open science practices and the underlying causal mechanisms. While each pathway differs in scope and context, the common approach highlights that Open Science practices can result in common effects which generate economic, societal or academic benefits. For instance, efficiency gains can result from savings in data storage costs, improved access to scientific publications, or improved data collection methods in Citizen Science projects. Such effects occur due to key underlying mechanisms, which can be summarised as access, transparency and participation (see forthcoming PaathOS D1.4). By pointing out these common impact pathways, PathOS contributes to a better understanding of academic, societal, and economic effects of different Open Science practices. The results can inform an improved design and monitoring of Open Science policies. In addition, the updated report demonstrates the feasibility of using the Key Impact Pathway approach for both a broad downstream as well as upstream analysis of open science practices and their impacts.

The report also discusses and highlights key limitations to the study of impacts. Being based on published literature studying specific impacts, the results may be affected by the streetlight effect and positivity bias. The Key Impact Pathways should thus be understood as indications of possible causal effects but should be further tested and verified using more rigorous study designs.

References

- Alkhawtani R.H.M.; Kwee T.C.; Kwee R.M. (2020). Citation advantage for open access articles in European Radiology, *European Radiology*, 30(1), 482-486. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00330-019-06389-0>
- Alvarez-Romero, C., Martinez-Garcia, A., Ternero Vega, J., et al. (2022). Predicting 30-Day Readmission Risk for Patients With Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease Through a Federated Machine Learning Architecture on Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) Data: Development and Validation Study. *JMIR Medical Informatics*, 10(6), e35307. <https://doi.org/10.2196/35307>
- Apartis S., G. Catalano, G. Consiglio, R. Costas, E. Delugas, M. Dulong de Rosnay, I. Grypari, I. Karasz, Thomas Klebel, E. Kormann, N. Manola, H. Papageorgiou, E. Seminaroti, P. Stavropoulos, L. Stoy, V.A. Traag, T. van Leeuwen, T. Venturini, S. Vignetti, ... T. Willemse. (2025). Open Science Impact Indicator Handbook (1.0.1) [Computer software]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14651106>
- Araujo, J. L.; Morais, C.; Paiva, J. C. (2022). Student participation in a coastal water quality citizen science project and its contribution to the conceptual and procedural learning of chemistry. *Chemistry Education Research and Practice*, 23(1), 100-112. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D1RP00190F>
- Bakker M, Veldkamp CLS, van Assen MALM, Crompvoets EAV, Ong HH, Nosek BA, et al. (2020) Ensuring the quality and specificity of preregistrations. *PLoS Biol* 18(12): e3000937. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.3000937>
- Barbrook-Johnson, P., Penn, A.S. (2022). Participatory Systems Mapping. In: *Systems Mapping*. Palgrave Macmillan, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-01919-7_5
- Besançon L., Peiffer-Smadja N., Segalas C.; Jiang H.; Masuzzo P., Smout C., Billy E., Deforet M., Leyrat C. (2021). Open science saves lives: lessons from the COVID-19 pandemic, *BMC Medical Research Methodology*, 21(1), 117. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12874-021-01304-y>
- Bezuidenhout, L., & Chakauya, E. (2018). Hidden concerns of sharing research data by low/middle-income country scientists. *Global Bioethics*, 29(1), 39-54. <https://doi.org/10.1080/11287462.2018.1441780>
- Bishop, B.W. & Collier, H.R. (2022). Fitness for use of data: scientists' heuristics of discovery and reuse behaviour framed by the FAIR Data Principles. *Information Research*, 27(3). <https://doi.org/10.47989/irpaper942>

- Björk B.-C.; Solomon D. (2014). How research funders can finance APCs in full OA and hybrid journals, *Learned Publishing*, 27(2), 93-103. <https://doi.org/10.1087/20140203>
- Bokonda, P.L., Ouazzani-Touhami, K. and Souissi, N. (2019) Open data kit: Mobile data collection framework for developing countries. *International Journal of Innovative Technology and Exploring Engineering*, 8(12), <https://www.ijitee.org/portfolio-item/L35831081219/>
- Boselli B., Galindo-Rueda F. (2016). Drivers and Implications of Scientific Open Access Publishing: Findings from a Pilot OECD International Survey of Scientific Authors. *OECD*. https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/science-and-technology/drivers-and-implications-of-scientific-open-access-publishing_5jlr2z70k0bx-en
- Boudreau, C. (2021). Reuse of open data in Quebec: from economic development to government transparency. *Public Administration*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0020852319884628>
- Brooks S.J., Fitch B., Davy-Bowker J., Codesal S.A. (2019). Anglers' Riverfly Monitoring Initiative (ARMI): A UK-wide citizen science project for water quality assessment. *Freshwater Science*, 38(2), 270-280. <https://doi.org/10.1086/703397>
- Bruckermann T.; Greving H.; Schumann A.; Stillfried M.; Börner K.; Kimmig S.E.; Hagen R.; Brandt M.; Harms U. (2021). To know about science is to love it? Unraveling cause-effect relationships between knowledge and attitudes toward science in citizen science on urban wildlife ecology. *Journal of Research in Science Teaching*, 58(8), 1179-1202. <https://doi.org/10.1002/tea.21697>
- Catalano, G., Caputo, A., Colnot, L., Delugas, E., Vignetti, S., Sousoni, D., Martins Grapengiesser, I., Pappas, D., Balsyte, E., Correia, A., Príncipe, P., Lopes, P., & Seminaroti, E. (2025). *Deliverable 4.4 – Cost-Benefit Analysis of Open Science: Case Study Synthesis and UniProt and RCAAP case studies*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15731712>
- Chen, X., Bharti, N., Marsteller, M.R. (2021). Use of Bibliometrics Data to Understand the Citation Advantages of Different Open Access Categories in Covid-19 Related Studies. *Proceedings of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 58(1), 410-414. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pra2.469>
- Cho J. (2021). Altmetrics of Highly Cited Research Papers in Social Science, *Serials Review*, 47(1), 17-27. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00987913.2021.1882652>
- Christensen, G., Dafoe, A., Miguel, E., Moore, D. A., & Rose, A. K. (2019). A study of the impact of data sharing on article citations using journal policies as a natural experiment. *PLOS ONE*, 14(12), e0225883. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0225883>

- Cole, N. L., Apartis, S., Balsyte, E., Correia, A., Garrard, C., Grypari, I., Martin, C., Papageorgiou, H., Principe, P., Sousoni, D., Stavropoulos, P., Traag, V., Venturini, T., & Willemse, T. (2023). PathOS - D3.1 Case studies for evaluation of open science impact. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10057051>
- Cole, N. L., Kormann, E., Klebel, T., Apartis, S., & Ross-Hellauer, T. (2024). The Figure 4-14 of Open Science—a scoping review. <https://doi.org/10.31235/osf.io/tqrwg>
- Coro, Gianpaolo. (2020). Open science and artificial intelligence supporting blue growth. *Environmental Engineering and Management Journal*. 19. 1719-1729. 10.30638/eemj.2020.162.
- Council of the European Union. 2023. Council Conclusions on High-quality, Transparent, Open, Trustworthy and Equitable Scholarly Publishing. <https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-8827-2023-INIT/en/pdf>
- Cox, T.E., Philippoff, J., Baumgartner, E., Smith, C.M. (2012). Expert variability provides perspective on the strengths and weaknesses of citizen-driven intertidal monitoring program. *Ecological Applications*, 22(4), 1202-1212. <https://doi.org/10.1890/11-1614.1>
- Crall A.W.; Newman G.J.; Stohlgren T.J.; Holfelder K.A.; Graham J.; Waller D.M. (2011). Assessing citizen science data quality: an invasive species case study. *Conservation Letters*, 4(6), 433-442. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1755-263X.2011.00196.x>
- Davis P.M., Fromerth M.J. (2007). Does the arXiv lead to higher citations and reduced publisher downloads for mathematics articles?, *Scientometrics*, 71(2), 203-215. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-007-1661-8>
- Deguines N., Princé K., Prévot A.-C., Fontaine B. (2020). Assessing the emergence of pro-biodiversity practices in citizen scientists of a backyard butterfly survey. *Science of The Total Environment*, 716, 136842. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.136842>
- Dehdarirad, T. and Didegah, F. (2020) 'To What Extent Does the Open Access Status of Articles Predict Their Social Media Visibility? A Case Study of Life Sciences and Biomedicine', *Journal of Altmetrics*, 3(1), p. 5. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.29024/joa.29>.
- Dekker, R., Karasz, I., & Stoy, L. (2023). PathOS - D1.1 Open Science Intervention Logic (Version v2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10418573>
- Delugas, E., Catalano, G., & Vignetti, S. (2023). PathOS - D4.1 Methodological note on the CBA of open science practices. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10277642>

Dorta-González P.; Dorta-González M.I. (2022). Contribution of the Open Access Modality to the Impact of Hybrid Journals Controlling by Field and Time Effects, *Journal of Data and Information Science*, 7(2), 57-83. <https://doi.org/10.2478/jdis-2022-0007>

Earp, H.S.; Liconti, A. (2020). Science for the Future: The Use of Citizen Science in Marine Research and Conservation, In: Jungblut, S., Liebich, V., Bode-Dalby, M. (eds) YOUMARES 9 - The Oceans: Our Research, Our Future. *Springer, Cham.*, 1-19. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-20389-4_1

Eger, T., Mertens, A., & Scheufen, M. (2021). Publication cultures and the citation impact of open access. *Managerial and Decision Economics*, 42(8), 1980-1998. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mde.3429>

European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, CWTS, Elsevier, ESADE, Lisbon Council, Switters, J.Osimo, D., (2019) *Electronic Laboratory Notebooks (ELNs) as key enablers of open science – Open science monitor case study*, Publications Office, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/07890>

European Commission (2021a). *Horizon Europe, open science – Early knowledge and data sharing, and open collaboration*. Publications Office of the European Union, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/18252>

European Commission (2021b). *SWD(2021)305 final. Better Regulation Guidelines*. https://commission.europa.eu/document/download/d0bbd77f-bee5-4ee5-b5c4-6110c7605476_en?filename=swd2021_305_en.pdf

European Commission (n.d.) *Open Source Strategy: History*. European Commission. Available at: https://commission.europa.eu/about-european-commission/departments-and-executive-agencies/digital-services/open-source-strategy-history_en [Accessed 28 Jun. 2025].

European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Athena-RIC, PPMI, Seureco-Erasme, UNU-MERIT, Stančiauskas, V., Brozaitis, H., Notten, A., Hollanders, H., Papageorgiou, H., Manola, N., Zagame, P., Le-Mouel, P., *Study to support the monitoring and evaluation of the framework programme for research and innovation along key impact pathways – Indicator methodology and metadata handbook*, Stančiauskas, V.(editor), Brozaitis, H.(editor), Notten, A.(editor), Hollanders, H.(editor), Papageorgiou, H.(editor), Manola, N.(editor), Zagame, P.(editor) and Le-Mouel, P.(editor), Publications Office of the European Union, 2022, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/44653>

Fahimifar, S., Mousavi, K., Mozaffari, F., & Ausloos, M. (2022). Identification of the most important external features of highly cited scholarly papers through 3 (i.e., Ridge, Lasso, and

- Boruta) feature selection data mining methods. *Quality & Quantity*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11135-022-01480-z>
- Fell M.J. (2019). The Economic Impacts of Open Science: A Rapid Evidence Assessment, *Publications*, 7(3), 46. <https://doi.org/10.3390/publications7030046>
- Fraser N., Momeni F., Mayr P., Peters I. (2019). Examining the citation and altmetric advantage of bioRxiv preprints. *International Conference on Scientometrics and Informetrics*. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Examining-the-citation-and-altmetric-advantage-of-Fraser-Momeni/b73e6b0af04d29e43bb23c57c02f899d52ff4c2d>
- Gries, C., Hanson, P. C., O'Brien, M., Servilla, M., Vanderbilt, K., & Waide, R. (2023). The Environmental Data Initiative: Connecting the past to the future through data reuse. *Ecology and Evolution*, 13(1), e9592. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ece3.9592>
- Grypari, I., Karasz, I., Klebel, T., Kormann, E., Manola, N., Papageorgiou, H., Stavropoulos, P., Stoy, L., van Leeuwen, T., Venturini, T., Waltman, L., Willemse, T., & Traag, V. (2023). PathOS - D2.1-D2.2-Open Science Indicator Handbook. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8305627>
- Hajjem C., Harnad S., Gingras Y. (2006). Ten-Year Cross-Disciplinary Comparison of the Growth of Open Access and How it Increases Research Citation Impact. *ArXiv*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.cs/0606079>
- Hardwicke T.E et al. 2018. Data availability, reusability, and analytic reproducibility: evaluating the impact of a mandatory open data policy at the journal *Cognition*. *R. Soc. open sci.* 5: 180448. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1098/rsos.180448>
- Harrison, P. W., Lopez, R., Rahman, N., Allen, S. G., Aslam, R., Buso, N., Cummins, C., Fathy, Y., Felix, E., Glont, M., Jayathilaka, S., Kadam, S., Kumar, M., Lauer, K. B., Malhotra, G., Mosaku, A., Edbali, O., Park, Y. M., Parton, A., & Apweiler, R. (2021). The COVID-19 Data Portal: accelerating SARS-CoV-2 and COVID-19 research through rapid open access data sharing. *Nucleic Acids Research*, 49(W1), W619–W623. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkab417>
- Heller, N., Rickman, J., Weight, C., & Papanikolopoulos, N. (2019). The Role of Publicly Available Data in MICCAI Papers from 2014 to 2018. *arXiv preprint*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1908.06830>
- Heumüller, R., Nielebock, S., Krüger, J. and Ortmeier, F. (2020) 'Publish or perish, but do not forget your software artifacts', *Empirical Software Engineering*. *Empir Software Eng* 25, 4585–4616. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10664-020-09851-6>

Holmberg, K., Hedman, J., Bowman, T. D., Didegah, F., & Laakso, M. (2020). Do articles in open access journals have more frequent altmetric activity than articles in subscription-based journals? An investigation of the research output of Finnish universities. *Scientometrics*, 122(1), 645-659. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-019-03301-x>

Jong S.; Slavova K. (2014). When publications lead to products: The open science conundrum in new product development, *Research Policy*, 43(4), 645-654. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2013.12.009>

Karasz, I., Stoy, L., Seminaroti, E., & Grapengiesser, I. M. (2024). *PathOS - D1.3 Key Impact Pathways for the Open Science Framework*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11108567>

Kelemen-Finan, J.; Scheuch, M.; Winter, S. (2018). Contributions from citizen science to science education: an examination of a biodiversity citizen science project with schools in Central Europe. *International Journal of Science Education International Journal of Science Education*, 40(17), 2078-2098. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09500693.2018.1520405>

Khan, D., Ashar, M., & Yuvaraj, M. (2022). Do open access journals have a greater citation impact? A study of journals in library and information science. *Collection and Curation*, 42(1), 13-24. <https://doi.org/10.1108/CC-03-2022-0010>

Khan, N., Thelwall, M., & Kousha, K. (2021). Measuring the impact of biodiversity datasets: data reuse, citations and altmetrics. *Scientometrics*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-021-03890-6>

Klebel, T., Cole, N. L., Tsipouri, L., Kormann, E., Karasz, I., Liarti, S., Stoy, L., Traag, V., Vignetti, S., & Ross-Hellauer, T. (2024). *PathOS - D1.2 Scoping Review of Open Science Impact*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10666427>

Klebel, Thomas & Traag, Vincent. (2024). Introduction to causality in science studies. *SocArXiv 4bw9e*, Center for Open Science. <https://doi.org/10.31235/osf.io/4bw9e>

Klebel, Thomas, Traag Vincent, Grypari Ioanna, Stoy Lennart and Ross-Hellauer Tony (2025). The academic impact of Open Science: a scoping review, *R. Soc. Open Sci.*12241248. <http://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.241248>

Kobayashi, S., Falcón, L., Fraser, H., Braa, J., Amarakoon, P., Marcelo, A. and Paton, C. (2021) *Using Open Source, Open Data, and Civic Technology to Address the COVID-19 Pandemic and Infodemic*. <https://www.thieme-connect.de/products/ejournals/abstract/10.1055/s-0041-1726488>

Laurinavichyute A., Yadav H., Vasishth S. 2022. Share the code, not just the data: A case study of the reproducibility of articles published in the Journal of Memory and Language under the

open data policy, *Journal of Memory and Language*, Volume 125, 104332. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jml.2022.104332>

Long H., Drown L., Amin M.E. (2022). The effect of open access on scholarly and societal metrics of impact in the ASHA Journals. *OSF Preprints*. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/2ufte>

Mahajan, S., Chung, M-K.; Martinez, J., Olaya, Y., Helbing, D., Chen, L-Y. (2022). Translating citizen-generated air quality data into evidence for shaping policy. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 9(1), 122. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-022-01135-2>

Marshall Z., Brunger F., Welch V., Asghari S., Kaposy C. (2018). Open Availability of Patient Medical Photographs in Google Images Search Results: Cross-Sectional Study of Transgender Research, *J Med Internet Res*, 20(2), e70. <https://doi.org/10.2196/jmir.8787>

McCabe, M.J., Snyder, C.M.. (2021). Cite unseen: Theory and evidence on the effect of open access on cites to academic articles across the quality spectrum. *Managerial and Decision Economics*, 41(8), 196-1979. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mde.3353>

McCormick M. M., Liu X., Ibanez L., Jomier J. , Marion C. (2014). ITK: enabling reproducible research and open science, *Frontiers in Neuroinformatics*, Volume 8 – 2014. <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/neuroinformatics/articles/10.3389/fninf.2014.00013>

McGillivray, B., Marongiu, P., Pedrazzini, N., Ribary, M., Wigdorowitz, M., & Zordan, E. (2022). Deep Impact: A Study on the Impact of Data Papers and Datasets in the Humanities and Social Sciences. *Publications*, 10, 39. <https://doi.org/10.3390/publications10040039>

McManamay, R. A., & Utz, R. M. (2014). Open-Access Databases as Unprecedented Resources and Drivers of Cultural Change in Fisheries Science. *Fisheries*, 39(10), 487–496. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03632415.2014.946128>

Miedzinski, M., Allinson, R., Arnold, E., Cassingena Harper, J., Doranova, A., Giljum, S., Griniece, E., Kubeczko, K., Mahieu, B., Markandya, A., Peter, V., Ploeg, M., Stasiakowska, A., Veen, G. (2013). *Assessing Environmental Impacts of Research and Innovation Policy*. Study for the European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Brussels. DOI:10.2777/5779

Moed H.F. (2007). The effect of "open access" on citation impact: An analysis of ArXiv's condensed matter section, *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology* 58(13), 2047-2054. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.20663>

Nelson, J. P., Lindsay, S., & Bozeman, B. (2023). The Last 20 Years of Empirical Research on Government Utilization of Academic Social Science Research: A State-of-the-Art Literature Review. *Administration & Society*, 55(8), 1479-1528. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00953997231172923>

Nguyen, P. Y., Kanukula, et al.. (2022). Changing patterns in reporting and sharing of review data in systematic reviews with meta-analysis of the effects of interventions: cross sectional meta-research study. *BMJ* (Clinical research ed.), 379, e072428. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj-2022-072428>

Open Knowledge. (2024). *What is Open Data?* Accessed at: 2025-02-01 <https://opendatahandbook.org/guide/en/what-is-open-data5/>

OSTP (2022). *Breakthroughs for All: Delivering Equitable Access to America's Research*. <https://www.whitehouse.gov/ostp/news-updates/2022/08/25/breakthroughs-for-all-delivering-equitable-access-to-americas-research/>

Piwovar, H. A., & Vision, T. J. (2013). Data reuse and the open data citation advantage. *PeerJ*, 1, e175. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.175>

Rabl, A. Peupartier (1995). B. Impact pathway analysis: A tool for improving environmental decision processes. *Environmental Impact Assessment Review*, 15(5), 421-442. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0195-9255\(95\)00044-F](https://doi.org/10.1016/0195-9255(95)00044-F)

Ratnieks F.L.W., Schrell F., Sheppard R.C., Brown E., Bristow O.E., Garbuzov M. (2016). Data reliability in citizen science: learning curve and the effects of training method, volunteer background and experience on identification accuracy of insects visiting ivy flower., *Methods in Ecology and Evolution*, 7(10), 1226-1235. <https://doi.org/10.1111/2041-210X.12581>

Reed, M. S., Ferré, M., Martin-Ortega, J., Blanche, R., Lawford-Rolfe, R., Dallimer, M., & Holden, J. (2021). Evaluating impact from research: A methodological framework. *Research Policy*, 50(4), 104147. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2020.104147>

Reinertsen, I., Collins, D.L. and Drouin, S. (2021) 'The essential role of open data and software for the future of ultrasound-based neuronavigation', *Frontiers in Oncology*, 10, Article 619274. [10.3389/fonc.2020.619274](https://doi.org/10.3389/fonc.2020.619274)

Ross-Hellauer T. (2017). What is open peer review? A systematic review [version 2; peer review: 4 approved]. *F1000Research*, 6:588. <https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.11369.2>.

Ross-Hellauer T., Horbach S.P.J.M., (2024). Additional experiments required: A scoping review of recent evidence on key aspects of Open Peer Review, *Research Evaluation*, Volume 33, rvae004. <https://doi.org/10.1093/reseval/rvae004>.

Santori C., Keith R.J., Whittington C.M., Thompson M.B., Van Dyke J.U., Spencer R.-J. (2021), Changes in participant behaviour and attitudes are associated with knowledge and skills gained

by using a turtle conservation citizen science app. *People and Nature*, 3(1), 66-76. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pan3.10184>

Schneider, J., Rosman, T., Kelava, A. and Merk, S. (2023) 'Do Open-Science Badges Increase Trust in Scientists Among Undergraduates, Scientists, and the Public?', *Psychological Science*, 33(9), 1588-1604. <https://doi.org/10.1177/09567976221097499>

Snijder, R. (2016). Revisiting an Open Access Monograph Experiment: Measuring Citations and Tweets 5 Years Later', *Scientometrics*, 109(3), 1855-1875. <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s11192-016-2160-6>

Sousoni, D. (n.d.). *Innovation from open research resources: A PathOS case study on bioinformatics*. PathOS Project. Retrieved April 2, 2025, from <https://pathos-project.eu/innovation-from-open-research-resources>

Spiegelman, E. (2021). Esteemed Colleagues: A Model of the Effect of Open Data on Selective Reporting of Scientific Results. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, 761168. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.761168>

Tang, M., Bever, J. D., & Yu, F.-H. (2017). Open access increases citations of papers in ecology. *Ecosphere*, 8(7). <https://doi.org/10.1002/ecs2.1887>

Thompson W.H., Wright J., Bissett P.J., Poldrack R.A. (2020). Meta-Research: Dataset decay and the problem of sequential analyses on open datasets, *eLife* 9:e53498. <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.53498>

Tsipouri, Lena, Sofia Liarti, Silvia Vignetti, and Izabella M. Grapengiesser (2025). The Economic Impact of Open Science: A Scoping Review. *MetaArXiv*. February 26. doi:10.31222/osf.io/kqse5_v1

UNESCO. (2021). UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science. <https://doi.org/10.54677/MNMMH8546>

Vadhera AS, Lee JS, Veloso IL, et al. Open Access Articles Garner Increased Social Media Attention and Citation Rates Compared With Subscription Access Research Articles: An Altmetrics-Based Analysis. *The American Journal of Sports Medicine*. 2022;50(13):3690-3697. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0363546522112488>

Van Vlijmen, H., et al. (2020). The need of industry to go FAIR. *Data Intelligence*, 2(1-2), 56-67. https://doi.org/10.1162/dint_a_00050

Walker D.W.; Smigaj M.; Tani M. (2021), The benefits and negative impacts of citizen science applications to water as experienced by participants and communities. *WIREs Water*, 8(1). <https://doi.org/10.1002/wat2.1488>

Wei M., Noroozi Chakoli A. (2020). Evaluating the relationship between the academic and social impact of open access books based on citation behaviours and social media attention, *Scientometrics*, 125(3), 2401-2420. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-020-03678-0>

Wilkinson, H., Hills, D., Penn, A., & Barbrook-Johnson, P. (2021). Building a system-based Theory of Change using Participatory Systems Mapping. *Evaluation*, 27(1), 80–101. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1356389020980493>

Wulder, M. A., Roy, D. P., Radeloff, V. C., Loveland, T. R., Anderson, M. C., Johnson, D. M., Healey, S., Zhu, Z., Scambos, T. A., Pahlevan, N., Hansen, M., Gorelick, N., Crawford, C. J., Masek, J. G., Hermosilla, T., White, J. C., Belward, A. S., Schaaf, C., Woodcock, C. E., Huntington, J. L., Lymburner, L., Hostert, P., Gao, F., Lyapustin, A., Pekel, J. F., Strobl, P., & Cook, B. D. (2022). Fifty years of Landsat science and impacts. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 280, 113195. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2022.113195>

Young J.S.; Brandes P.M. (2020). Green and gold open access citation and interdisciplinary advantage: A bibliometric study of two science journals. *The Journal of Academic Librarianship*, 46(2), 102105. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acalib.2019.102105>